

Qualitative Case Study Exploring Operational Barriers Impeding Small and Private, Non-profit Higher Education Institutions from Implementing Information Security Controls

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Approval Page

Qualitative Case Study Exploring Operational Barriers Impeding Small and Private, Non-profit Higher Education Institutions from Implementing Information Security Controls

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Abstract

The higher education industry uses the very latest technologies to effectively prepare students for their careers, but these technologies often contain vulnerabilities that can be exploited via their connection to the Internet. The complex task of securing information and computing systems is made more difficult at institutions of higher education due to philosophical traditions of academic freedom as well as growing budgetary constraints and intransigent stakeholder expectations of unimpeded access to educational and entertainment resources. This qualitative multi-case study examined small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education to understand the challenges that technology managers face in securing these systems. Technology leaders at eight of these institutions were interviewed to determine the priority of information security, operational barriers that impede the implementation of effective security controls, current problems and issues that inhibited security controls, and what additional resources were necessary to implement security controls according to best practices. Insights, innovations, strategies, and common issues were sought during the interviews to create a foundational conversation for stakeholders. The findings indicated that there were significant operational barriers to computing security at institutions of higher education. A lack of institutional support and comprehension was found at all of the interviewed institutions and education of leadership at all levels is necessary as a first step to the development of a strategy. Additionally, a formal security framework should be adopted that will serve as a guide and a means of feedback to these institutions. This work should enable

Information Technology leaders in higher education to develop a vision that supports a holistic and organized approach to computing security.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

The higher education industry strives to provide students with a high-quality education using the latest, varying technologies (Dennen, 2015). However, these technologies are vulnerable to computer system attack from any corner of the earth using the Internet as a means to access inadequately protected computer networks and systems (Knapp & Ferrante, 2012). Securing digital information in any industry is challenging and even more so at institutions of higher education due to inherent impediments that include traditions of academic freedom, budgetary constraints, the use of vulnerable computer systems, and expectations of unimpeded access to educational and entertainment resources (Asllani, 2012; Bartolacci, Le Blanc & Podhradsky, 2014; Hodgman, 2014; Kam & Katerattanakul, 2014).

The operational impediments to information security at these organizations are not easily navigated because of pressures from internal and external stakeholders that do not want to part with long-standing traditions and expectations that may run contrary to information security. For example, institutions of higher education pride themselves on the philosophical principles and traditions of academic freedom and openness and view incursions on these sacred principles as attacks on the educational and research system (Kam & Katerattanakul, 2014). Additionally, students and faculty demand access to academic and entertainment resources regardless of the risks they pose to the institution (Asllani, 2012; Bartolacci et al., 2014). These deeply held stakeholder expectations along with budgetary pressures to keep a college education affordable can significantly impede information security efforts (Hodgman, 2014).

Attacks of information residing on computer systems are becoming more sophisticated and frequent, and institutions of higher education need to be adequately prepared. The 1,269 small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. are particularly vulnerable to computer system attacks due to limited resources, inadequate skillsets, and limited vision and understanding (Bougaardt & Kyobe, 2011; Holter & Seganish, 2014; IPEDS, 2015; Sangani, Vijayakumar, & Pilani, 2012). These collective weaknesses present a dilemma for information security managers because they must balance the philosophical and strategic academic mandates, budgetary constraints, and stakeholder expectations with the need for sound information security practices.

Background

Businesses have become more dependent on computing resources and the Internet to increase productivity, quality, and availability of products and services but insufficient security of digital assets represents a threat to the livelihood of their business models (Jalal-Karim, 2013). Businesses are attempting to address computing security threats in order to secure their data and information from source to destination (Miseviciene, Ambraziene, Tuminauskas, & Pazereckas, 2012). Many large corporations and businesses have adequate resources to address the increasing information security concerns, however, small to medium enterprises (SME) do not have adequate resources, vision, and skillsets to effectively implement security controls (Sangani et al., 2012). The higher education industry is currently under enormous pressure to keep costs down due to reduced funding from state agencies as well as political campaigns that vow to make education more affordable (Hodgman, 2014). Therefore, these institutions are forced to do more with less amid fierce competition for scarce financial resources and information

security initiatives are often left unfunded (Holter & Seganish, 2014; Sangani et al., 2012).

Information security at colleges and universities is typically a source of contention between information security personnel and users because of the contradiction of long-standing traditions of academic freedom and openness with best practice security guidelines (Reichman et al., 2014). Additionally, there are many stakeholders at small and private, non-profit colleges and universities that believe that they are not a target because of the limited value of their information (Sangani et al., 2012). However, the recent publicized breaches of information systems at educational institutions and the ensuing negative publicity has created a shift in priority which has brought to the forefront the challenges associated with the implementation of effective information security controls balanced with long-standing traditions of openness in the higher education industry (Al-Ibrahim, 2012).

A review of the literature revealed there were some studies that addressed higher education obstacles related to computing security but none have addressed all of these obstacles in aggregate. In addition, it was necessary to broaden the search to include works that addressed the small size characteristic of these institutions of higher education because they represented the target population of the study. This was accomplished by including works about small and medium enterprises (SME) related to computing security because these organizations closely mirrored the environment at small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. The works pertaining to computing security from all business organizations were utilized to fill in the gaps on issues like security benchmarks, security strategies, human factor risks, and overall

threats where no work existed that was specific to higher education. This piecemeal approach to the collection of works related to this topic underscores the need for further study in this area.

Statement of the Problem

College and University users expect all campus computing resources and environments to be reliable, fast, safe, ubiquitous, and secure. However, there are limited resources to accomplish those expectations (Stewart, 2012). As a result, technology managers find it extremely challenging to balance stakeholder expectations with information security best practices and must strategically assign precious monetary and human resources to formulate an effective security strategy (Stewart, 2012). If budgetary, philosophical, and strategic higher education mandates must be satisfied along with sound information security, then technology managers must prioritize, innovate, and carefully weigh the benefits and drawbacks of investments in security solutions as well as their impact on the campus community.

The overall business problem that was explored consisted of determining and understanding the importance of information security at these small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. Because most small to medium enterprises (SME) do not believe that they are truly at risk due to their belief that their institutions do not represent a desirable target for hackers, too little attention and resources are devoted to information security (Sangani et al., 2012). Additionally, campus stakeholders are unwilling to compromise their positions on academic freedom, allocation of additional monetary resources, submission of information systems to rigorous security tests, and access to entertainment systems for additional security

(Asllani, 2012; Bartolacci et al., 2014; Hodgman, 2014; Kam & Katerattanakul, 2014).

The specific business problem that was examined consisted of determining the proper priority and allocation of information security resources so that effective solutions and strategies are implemented that balance the needs of stakeholders with information security best practices. A balanced information security approach is necessary because it must take into account the available financial resources of the institution as well as the environment in which it operates (Kam & Katerattanakul, 2014; Knapp & Ferrante, 2012; Sangani et al., 2012).

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this qualitative, descriptive multi-case study was to examine eight institutions from the population of 1,269 small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. that grant a bachelor's degree and explore the impact that their unique computing requirements and expectations had on the effectiveness of their implementation of information security controls. Information security controls consist of hardware, software, outsourcing and consultative resources, departmental skillsets, and training methodologies for department personnel as well as the entire campus community in relation to their current computing network security implementation. Data was gathered from the selected institutions using semi-structured telephone interviews of those responsible for information security to ascertain how the unique operational impediments in the higher education context affected their implemented security solutions. The interviews attempted to discover key indicators, contributing factors, insights, perspectives, and innovations related to the efficacy of implemented information

security strategies and controls as well as the perceived effectiveness of the security strategies by the security leaders.

Theoretical Framework

This multi-case study contained four themes generated from a review of the literature which represented a broad perspective of issues related to information security within colleges and universities that included information security threats to educational information systems, the human factor as part of information security concerns, information security strategies, and impediments to information security in higher education. Detailed research questions were created from these themes based on a review of the literature. The theoretical aspect of the human factor information security theme was addressed using the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) which examines users' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (PBC) along with antecedent beliefs to predict behavioral intention and, ultimately, actual behavior (Ajzen, 1991). The value of studying relevant attitudes, subjective norms, and PBC can lead to security training, programs, interventions, and awareness campaigns that can enhance information security (Hu, Dinev, Hart, & Cooke, 2012). It can also aid in the understanding of the stakeholder perceptions of security programs.

The remaining three information security themes were represented within all of the constructs and fit within the theoretical framework of Organizational Learning Theory (OLT). OLT can be understood as a cyclical process that recognizes errors, corrects them, and then looks for other errors (Huang & Shih, 2011). Single loop organizational learning consists of determining that a result is not consistent with expectations, which leads to change in action within the confines of recognized

institutional systems (Huang & Shih, 2011). Double loop organizational learning is more radical in nature and can affect change to value systems and operational parameters to completely change a process or an organization to implement a change when expectations are not met (Huang & Shih, 2011).

Because it may not be practical to believe that traditional, well-established academic institutions can readily implement radical changes required by double loop learning, single loop learning was the environment in which operational parameters were examined. Single loop OLT changes related to limited budgets, limited skillsets, academic freedom, residential computing expectations, wireless availability, and distance learning infrastructure were addressed across the three themes consisting of information security threats, vulnerabilities in higher education information systems, information security strategies, and obstacles to information security. The TPB was used to examine attitudes, subjective norms, beliefs, and behaviors related to the academic freedom philosophy subscribed to by faculty, student expectations of open entertainment in university networks, and overall stakeholder perceptions of the efficacy of implemented information security solutions. The combination of the TPB and the OLT provided a firm foundation for this multi-case study related to impediments to information security within institutions of higher education in the U.S.

Research Questions

The research questions aid in enhanced focus and deeper understanding of the case and typically answer the questions of how and why (Yin, 2014). The proposed research questions implied that information security controls at colleges and universities were challenging to implement as supported by a review of the literature. The researcher

sought to gain a thorough understanding of the nature of these challenges including why they are present and how information security personnel have managed the technological and human aspects of their strategies and implementations. The research questions that were created provided a framework for the development of the semi-structured interview questions that were used for the interviews of the participants.

- Q1.** Which operational barriers impede small and private, non-profit higher education institutions from implementing information security controls?
- Q2.** Why are current provisions lacking in the ability to maintain information security controls?
- Q3.** What resources are needed to address operational barriers in the implementation of information security controls?

Nature of the Study

A qualitative, descriptive, multi-case study was utilized to study the efficacy of implemented computing security solutions in small, private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. both from the perspective of computing security personnel as well as from users. The case study research method typically answers how and why questions and is ideal to gain a deeper understanding of complex phenomena rather than only focusing on frequency of occurrence (Yin, 2014). This multi-case study focused on the insights generated about a phenomenon rather than the cases themselves, which is known as an instrumental case (Stake, 2006).

Case study research involves creating and organizing a study using research questions as a foundation and then interpreting and experiencing a phenomenon in its original habitat related to these research question using observational techniques to

generate a more complete understanding of the phenomenon so that it can be portrayed to others (Stake, 2006). A multi-case study methodology is ideal when conclusions across numerous cases are sought and is stronger than a single case design because multiple cases offer more compelling evidence than a single case (Yin, 2014). Multi-case studies are best with more than three cases but less than ten because too few cases results in limited conclusions that can be identified during multi-case analysis and too many cases results in too much data to process for deeper understanding (Stake, 2006). The number of cases selected for a study should not be analogous to a sample size in a quantitative study but should rather be determined by the strength of the conclusions desired by the researcher and the elimination of rival explanations (Yin, 2014). Therefore, a replicative approach was used that drew on eight cases to strengthen the conclusions of the study and eliminate rival explanations. The researcher randomly selected eight cases from the total population of small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. for inclusion in this study.

This multi-case study contained four themes generated from a review of the literature which represented a broad perspective of issues related to information security within colleges and universities that included information security threats to higher education information systems, the human factor as part of information security concerns, information security strategies and impediments to information security in higher education. These four themes along with the three research questions drove the propositions and the participant interview questions.

Significance of the Study

This study was significant because of the growing threats to the information systems at educational institutions and reflects the importance of effective information security at all of these institutions but particularly at small and private, non-profit colleges and universities with significant financial and resource challenges. However, this study was not only about playing information security catch-up and lack of resources in small educational institutions of higher learning but, rather, was more fundamentally about the unique impediments that require IT leadership responsible for information security at these institutions to balance the philosophical and strategic academic mandates with sound information security practices. The overall importance of this study was to bring to the forefront the dilemma faced by small educational institutions, to raise awareness, assess the overall landscape of the issues, determine the level of risk, and understand how they affect the respective information security implementations. The findings of this study provide insights and strategies to information security personnel at colleges and universities about how other institutions are dealing with these challenges amid budgetary shortages and pressures from academic users. This study also provides a foundation for stakeholder conversations based on the perspective of personnel who are responsible for the security of campus information technologies.

Definition of Key Terms

Academic freedom. A fundamental philosophical principle in higher education that grants scholars privileges and rights to actively engage in discussions of varied ideas without retribution (Kam & Katerattanakul, 2014).

Biometrics. A method of identity verification that utilizes a person's physical

characteristics or an identifying behavior of that person so that secure access to an information system can be granted (Ogini, 2013).

Breach. A condition of an information system that is characterized by unauthorized access or entry that is intended to do harm to a victim or provide an advantage or enrichment to the attacker (Wall, 2013).

Case study. An empirical study methodology that focuses on a phenomenon within the actual environment in which it occurs to ascertain a deeper understanding and insights taking into account the critical component of context (Yin, 2014).

Cloud-based computing. A remote computing model that offers infrastructure, software, application and platforms in an outsourced context to create efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and convenience for organizations (Arpaci et al., 2014).

Computing security/Information security. The relative safety of computing resources and information based on the principles of confidentiality, integrity and availability of resources to authorized individuals (SansD, 2014).

Cyber-insurance. A risk insurance product that intends to protect against potential cyber-attack as part of a risk mitigation approach to network computing security by spreading the risk among many clients (Shackelford, 2012).

Denial of service/Personal denial of service. A means of cyber-attack that bombards a network or a particular user with network traffic or access routines designed to overwhelm the system so as not to allow access to computing resources (Bartolacci et al., 2014).

IT or Information Technology. Computing hardware and software resources used to provide users with access to efficient access to information resources and

communication using digital transport through a medium (SansN, 2014).

ISO27001. An International Standards Organization computing security model that provides a systematic framework for implementation, maintenance, and improvement of information security (Gillies, 2011).

Network or Network infrastructure. A grouping of computing resources that allows for trusted access to information, communication and sharing of resources (SansN, 2014).

Phishing. A social engineering tactic where a user is duped or spoofed into giving usernames, passwords or other proprietary information to hackers (Purkait, 2012).

Ransomware. Software that is created to forcibly encrypt all or most files on a remote computing system using a complex key that leads to extortion of funds from the user (Oluga et al., 2014).

Security controls. Computing policies and procedures implemented to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information and computing resources (SansD, 2014).

Threats. Actors or activities that pose a danger to a computer network and information by taking advantage of a weakness or vulnerability in the system (SansD, 2014).

Virtualization. A software technology that allows multiple host operating systems to share a single physical host computer's resources to achieve cost savings through efficiency and rapid creation of host computers (Miseviciene et al., 2012).

Vulnerabilities. A weakness of a computer network, information system, or computing resources that could be taken advantage of by a particular threat (SansD,

2014).

Web-based computing. A computer system that exchanges information, communication and other computing resources using a web browser as a user interface on a host computing system using scripting and other web-based technologies (Jalal-Karim, 2013).

WEP. An early wireless encryption protocol implementation that was created from the IEEE standards committee to provide a comparable amount of security to a wired network (Budhrani & Sridaran, 2015).

Wireless or Wireless computing. A computing network infrastructure that uses radio frequency waves in the air as the medium by which communication and information exchange occur (Budhrani & Sridaran, 2015).

WPA. A wireless security protocol implementation that is an enhancement to the original WEP protocol that uses a temporal key integrity protocol for stronger encryption (Budhrani & Sridaran, 2015).

Summary

This qualitative multi-case study focused on information security operational barriers and challenges faced by small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education. Personnel from eight institutions of higher education were interviewed to assess their insights, strategies, challenges, and recommended solutions related to the implementation of information security controls at their institutions. Questions pertaining to the operational barriers that impede effective information security controls were posed along with queries about problems and issues with current solutions. Additionally, these personnel were asked to provide recommendations about the

appropriate level of resources needed to address the operational barriers and allow for more effective security solutions to be implemented.

This study not only brought to the forefront the importance of effective information system security at these institutions along with the operational barriers encountered by information security personnel, but also provided insights and strategies from higher educational information security personnel who are actively confronting these issues on a daily basis. This study provides a sound basis for conversations to be held regarding the best means of implementing these solutions that take into account the needs of all campus stakeholders. A thorough review of the literature in chapter two provides a firm foundation for this study and helped generate the research questions and the interview questions.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The purpose of this study was to examine small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. to determine the impact of their operational and contextual characteristics on the efficacy of their computing security strategies and solutions. The scope of the study encompassed the vulnerabilities of educational information systems, user interaction with these systems, and the unique challenges that were present as a result of operational, philosophical, and traditional approaches to their mission. Information Technology leadership were interviewed to ascertain their perspective about computing security. These interviews provided rich descriptions, strategies, and insights that shed light on the unique challenges that stakeholders at these institutions face along with strategies and potential solutions. The study purpose drove the literature review and the selection of works were focused on relevant topics that provided information to support it.

The academic literature related to information security presents a variety of topics, which vary greatly in focus and purpose. The review of the literature with respect to the study topic required a narrowing of the search terms to elicit relevant works that provided a foundation and support structure for the topic context. Four themes emerged from the discrimination of works pertaining to the topic of study, which included (1) threats and vulnerabilities to information systems of higher education; (2) the human factor related to threats of security; (3) existing models and strategies of computing security; and (4) impediments to higher educational information computing security. These themes were used to create the research questions and premise of the study, which directed its flow and focus.

Documentation

The research domain contained an abundant amount of literature related to information security but some of the information was not relevant to the current study. Saturation of the first theme, higher education information system vulnerabilities, did not occur quickly due to the large amount of threats to educational systems and the varied perspectives of studies performed in the last five years. This caused the researcher to select more works from this theme than others in order to provide an adequate understanding of the broad threats that were faced by educational institutions. The human factor and strategy themes were also well-represented in the literature and saturation occurred after approximately 26 works were selected from each category. The final theme, higher education impediments and challenges, contained a sum of the works related to challenges specific to institutions of higher education as well as those that related to the size of the institution. The impediments related to the size of the institutions were represented by works relative to small and medium enterprises (SME) which have characteristics that are very similar to small colleges and universities. The search themes, terms, and database resources used in the literature review are described in Table 1.

Information Security Threats to Educational Information Systems

The discussion of educational information security threats was undertaken by examining the literature that enumerated the presence of broad threats in the cyber space environment before concentrating on threats specific to educational information systems. This broad focus provided a more thorough understanding of the threat vector in which

Table 1
Review of the Literature Search Strategy and Themes

Themes	Searches	Sources Selected
Threats and vulnerabilities to higher education learning technologies	"higher education" + cyber + security + vulnerability + risk + wireless + mobile + online + learning + cloud + college + university + web + applications + privacy + attack + threat + copyright + gaming + "social media" + denial	37
Human factor considerations to information security, Policies, Procedures, Training, Education	"weakest Link" + cyber + security + "human factor" + insider + phishing + training + education + abuse + motivations + intentional + policies + procedures	27
Strategies, assessment, investment, insurance	strategies + metrics + cyber + security + models + frameworks + assessment + controls + authentication	27
Small college/SME impediments, obstacles and constraints to information security	" higher education" + constraints + impediments + "academic freedom" + SME + costs + obstacles + budgets + lax + expertise + risks + criminals + target + behavior + college + university	25
Note: The primary database used was the North Central University Roadrunner Discovery Service. Other databases searched included Proquest, Ebscohost, ACM Digital Library and Google Scholar.		Total=116

educational information systems operate and highlighted the need for thorough preparation as well as an effective computing security strategy. Many of the threats described in the broader landscape not only defined the many dangers present, but also provided a clear contrast to the approach to information security employed by many small educational institutions.

There are many threats to the information systems of organizations and the number and scope of these threats has greatly increased in the past decade due to emerging technologies that have had a significant impact on our world. Oluga et al. (2014) generated a comprehensive list of threats that affect a wide range of industries and functions, which need to be considered when formulating a security strategy. Desi and Patel (2013) corroborated these threats and, like Oluga et al., generated a very specific

list of cyber-crimes about which computer users need to be aware. These threats varied widely and affected not only businesses but all computer users in general.

These broad threats affect all computer users because many of the daily activities of computer users require interaction with cyberspace. The varied threats to different industries include journalism, politics, government, socialization, tourism, medicine, advertising, commerce, entertainment, learning, and many others (Oluga et al., 2014). Specific threats to individual users in cyberspace are numerous and include email abuse, pornography, defamation, stalking, harassment, and bullying (Desi & Patel, 2013). Desi and Patel noted that each one of these threats can have many manifestations such as the email threat which may include spamming, impersonation, bombing, and phishing. Many of these threats are criminal in nature and intend to do harm to an individual or business but may also seek to enrich the perpetrator.

There are also threats that occur on a global basis and may be sponsored or perpetrated by nation states. Spalevic (2014) described threats that emanated from these sources which could be classified as cyber warfare and involved very sophisticated attacks that were intended to do harm to targets within other countries (Spalevic, 2014). The attacks described by Spalevic were typically well-funded and organized and had very specific political motivations. Oluga et al. (2014) also made mention of these nation-sponsored threats by listing actual manifestations including cyber espionage, terrorism, and warfare. These researchers discussed the granular components of the sophisticated threats which included malware, blackmail, piracy, spoofing, denial of service (DOS), fraud, impersonation, and defamation. All of these harmful cyber activities described a very volatile and dangerous landscape in which users and industry operate and

underscored the importance of taking precautions to prevent an incursion.

The threats to educational information systems have been the topic of study for a great many works in the literature. The risks to institutions of higher education encompass not only the threats noted by Oluga et al. (2014) and Spalevic (2014) but also consist of information security threats that originate inside the institution. Many of the threats result from the varied technologies employed by educational institutions as well as a lack of awareness about how these systems can be compromised.

One of the greatest threats to educational institutions of higher education is due to the adoption of eLearning or online learning systems that automate and support some pedagogical functions. A 2012 work produced by Ben Arfa Rabai, Rabai, and Ben Aissa, highlighted some of the many vulnerabilities that were present in eLearning including denial of service, search spam, and key loggers. Chen and He (2013) also enumerated risks to eLearning systems that included address resolution protocol (ARP) cache poisoning, brute force attack, cross-site attacks, DOS, spoofing, impersonation, structured query language (SQL) injection, rootkit attacks, hijacking, stack smash, and session number prediction. Zamzuri, Manag, Yunus, and Ahmad (2013) listed spoofing, tampering, repudiation, information disclosure, denial of service, and unauthorized elevation of privilege as important eLearning vulnerabilities that need to be considered in an eLearning adoption strategy. Costinela-Luminita and Magdalena (2012) itemized eLearning vulnerabilities that included cross site scripting, SQL injection, password cracking, session identification guessing, remote injection of viruses, web searches for private information, and site forgery attempts. Finally, Muazu and Lawal (2012) performed a study that surveyed users of eLearning systems to ascertain their perceived

greatest eLearning threats which produced responses that cited human error, deliberate attack, and vandalism. It is clear that eLearning systems have many vulnerabilities which need to be addressed in order for this technology to realize its full potential and to be used in a secure manner.

The literature also offered rationale for why eLearning systems were at risk. Ben Arfa Rabai et al. (2012) explained that eLearning systems are at risk because they have a broad attack surface with many components which consist of web servers, database servers, networks, and client computers. Chen and He (2013) held that security is lacking in eLearning systems because educational institutions are quick to adopt these technologies without full comprehension of the security risks involved. Zamzuri et al. (2013) agreed that there are many risks with eLearning systems and noted that these systems have the potential to increase productivity so they are adopted quickly without a full realization of the risks. Asllani (2012) also argued that eLearning systems were adopted too quickly without careful thought to security because of the favorable financial and practical benefits of this mode of learning. Yunus and Zamzuri (2013) related that eLearning systems were adopted without proper preparation because they have the capability to improve the quality of the pedagogical process but users are not always aware of the risks. Moreover, the financial and operational benefits of these systems has led to their rapid and widespread adoption which has provided a means of ingress for potential intruders in those systems that were not implemented in a secure manner.

There were strategies and remedies highlighted in the literature that focused on ways the security risks from these systems could be mitigated. Dennen (2015) explained that institutions should implement training, awareness programs, and policies that

delineate best practices in the secure use of eLearning systems. Mandala, Abdullah, and Ismail (2013) provided a comprehensive list of remedies for eLearning security that included the implementation of enhancements to privacy identity management, web-based protection that includes firewalls and virtual private networks, digital rights management of content, secure transmission using authentication certificates, intrusion detection systems, and intrusion prevention systems. These strategies represent the best practices in securely implementing eLearning systems which can benefit both users and producers of these systems.

The literature also provided insights related to information security that explained why users may not fully utilize or participate in eLearning systems. Lorenz, Sousa, and Tomberg (2012) found that there was a correlation between user-perceived privacy of information and the intention to fully participate in the use of eLearning systems. This means that students will not fully engage in the use of these systems unless they are aware of due diligence to secure the information they provide during learning exercises. May, Fessakis, Dimitracopoulou, and George (2012) concur that user perception of adequate security is a key factor in the eLearning context and argued that it can be a barrier to learning if students are not convinced their information is secure. Dennen (2015) views the eLearning interaction between instructors and learners as an opportunity to instill in learners good eLearning security practices so that learners feel comfortable in providing full participation in this learning environment. Because eLearning systems are continuously changing and evolving, it is important to adopt a set of security best practices that address the dynamic nature of these systems and instills confidence in users regarding the secure storage and transfer of information.

Institutions of higher education utilize many other web-based systems besides eLearning systems that may also be vulnerable to attacks. These systems include enterprise resource systems, eCommerce systems, departmental systems, and websites that advertise the institution as well as provide access to information and services (Al-Ibrahim, 2012). Jalal and Karim (2013) discussed the benefits of web-based systems that enhance and automate business functions but also described the associated risks to these systems of potential theft, modification, and malicious activities. Al-Ibrahim (2012) agrees that security is at risk in the many potential uses of web-based system in the educational context such as collaboration, grading, lectures, and dissemination of information, training, conferences, distance learning, assignments, and research. Vakharia, Mishra, and Kumar (2013) detailed the vulnerabilities of web-based eCommerce systems and noted that educational institutions make use of these types of systems in their daily business activities. Al-Ibrahim and Al-Deen in their 2014 study examined educational websites and their vulnerabilities and noted the great importance of securing them. As these researchers have described, the web is a very powerful technology that offers convenience and flexibility for business transactions but it is critical that this technology be adopted in a secure manner to avoid breaches that could have long term negative consequences.

The literature provides remedies for securing web-based systems that can reduce the risks and provide confidence of security to users. Vakharia et al. (2013) were very specific about ways to secure web-based systems including penetration tests, web monitoring software, internal and external security audits, automated security tools, and email monitoring tools. Al-Ibrahim and Al-Deen (2014) recommended remedies that

included the elimination of broken links on websites, installation of the latest patches to combat cross-site scripting, secure web form design, secure configuration of web server, masking of email addresses, disallowing uploads to a website, fixing of configuration errors, elimination of auto-complete for passwords, and masking of web server characteristics. Al-Ibrahim (2012) also made recommendations to increase the security of web-based educational systems that included the dedication of employees to an information security department, implementation of security auditing procedures, setting high standards for the adoption of systems, training of web design personnel in secure practices, utilization of security features on systems, and the use of secure browsing to sites. All of these recommendations provided best practices on how to secure web-based systems at educational institutions but also offered insights into the complexities of these systems as well as the need for institutions to dedicate adequate resources to address their secure implementation.

Colleges and Universities employ many other technologies designed to enhance the teaching and learning process but also put the institution at risk. These technologies include mobile technologies, wireless systems, cloud computing, and entertainment systems. Cloud computing, a means to share pooled computing resources at a remote geographic location, is vulnerable in the educational context as described by Arpaci, Kilicer and Bardakci (2014) mainly due to privacy and security issues. Polonetsky and Tene (2014) agreed that security in the use of cloud-based systems is a major concern and argued that an environment of trust must be created to facilitate the effective use of these systems. Modi, Patel, Borisaniya, Patel, and Rajarajan (2012) detailed security concerns specific to cloud computing including address resolution protocol (ARP) spoofing,

domain name system (DNS) poisoning, man in the middle attacks, packet flooding, and router attacks. Moreover, the loss of control and reliance upon a third party to care for servers and software creates a potential lack of security and trust.

Wireless systems also present a challenge for information security at educational institutions because their inherent accessible nature of information in the airwaves makes them difficult to secure. Wireless systems are vulnerable to man in the middle attacks, denial of service, rogue access points, sniffing of data, and social engineering threats according to Noor and Hassan (2013). These authors explained that wireless hacking tools are widely available and even novice computer users can make use of them for dark purposes. Budhrani and Sridaran (2015) agree that wireless systems pose a threat to organizations and attributed the popularity of these systems to convenience, mobility, flexibility, low cost, ubiquity, and ease of access. Wireless computing offers great flexibility, according to these researchers, and historically not much attention has been paid to security. However, they noted that recent enhancements in the security of wireless protocols such as wireless equivalency protocol (WEP) and Wi-Fi protected access (WPA) has led to greater security if they are properly implemented. This has allowed a means to add a greater measure of security to these systems, however, many institutions do make use of WPA and still use WEP which is susceptible to attack.

Wireless technology represents the foundation for mobile technology, which has become more pervasive in both businesses and education and now represents one of the biggest challenges for security personnel to date. Bring your own device (BYOD) or bring your own technology (BYOT), as it is more recently known, represents a large security challenge for organizations according to Miller, Voas and Hurlburt (2012). The

widespread availability of these devices at an affordable cost, according to these authors, has led to their integration into the business environment and the educational environment. However, the use of these mobile devices, according to Kambourakis (2013), has brought an increasing threat to security and privacy as both a personal aid and teaching and learning device. This highlighted the notion that both instructors and students need to be wary of the dangers associated with the use of BYOD and seek ways to mitigate risks in its use.

Shonola and Joy (2014) presented two works related to mobile technology security in institutions of higher education; one from the perspective of student users and the other from the perspective of educators. The paper they presented from the perspective of users described the threats that students faced when using BYOD for learning purposes that included loss or theft of device, malware infestation, unauthorized access to content, and denial of service to mobile learning servers. Their study from the perspective of educators revealed security vulnerabilities in the form of unauthorized sharing of copyrighted materials, data interception, student exploitation of privacy, unauthorized access to course content, and the dissemination of false information.

Shonola and Joy (2015) also presented a comprehensive analysis of mobile learning that argued that too many educational institutions are rushing to take advantage of the BYOD technology without fully considering the impact of using what has been produced by companies that are motivated primarily by sales of devices rather than security of operation. These works provide a basic understanding of the concerns with mobile learning security that institutional security personnel should understand as well as the complexities in securing them.

Student, faculty, and staff use of entertainment aspects of the computing infrastructure of educational institutions adds another layer of vulnerability to the organization. Popescul and Georgescu (2015) underscored the necessity that universities redefine their security policies to account for social networking due to vulnerabilities caused from its simplicity of use, transparency of information, and ease of access. These researchers explained that the boundaries of social media systems are global and can include those that intend harm by providing them with anonymity. Benson, Saridakas, and Tennakoon (2015) was also concerned with the risks related to social media and related that the informality of social media encourages users to let down their guard and disregard privacy and security considerations. The vulnerability to educational institutions adopting social media for use as part of the curriculum, according to these authors, has exacerbated the need for awareness programs, training initiatives, and security controls to reduce the risk of using these systems. Gaming is another very popular entertainment outlet for students who were found to dedicate 7.46 hours per week to their use according to Hainey, Connolloy, Stransfield, and Boyle (2011). The broad popularity of gaming has led to studies that have examined its viability as an educational tool but this, too, has risks due to improper consideration of security in its implementation according to Hainey et al. (2011). The widespread popularity and use of these systems suggests institutional security personnel should be aware of the impact on their security strategy and take steps to educate users on secure practices.

There are also many other student-related internal security risks because they possess access to a powerful network infrastructure for leisure activities that can lead to various forms of misbehavior. Selwyn (2008) studied the educational context related to

student interaction and found that it was conducive to misbehavior because of the nearness to possible victims, plentiful network capacity, limited supervision, absence of maturity, and strong technical skills. Bartolacci, LeBlanc, and Podhradsky (2014) studied manifestations of misbehavior at educational institutions which consisted of personal denial of service (PDoS) attacks, intimidation, and other practices of harassment related to computing. Hazelwood and Koon-Magnin (2013) explained that the Internet provides a new way to harass, threaten, intimidate, and inflict harm on people. As a result, these authors argued that legislative protections are necessary to discourage this type of behavior but the anonymity of users as well as the geographically diverse location of users makes these misbehaviors very difficult to prevent. Finally, gaming misbehaviors are also very common in educational institutions and may cause security threats to an organization. Teng, Tseng, Chen, and Wu (2102) voiced these concerns in their study by describing the potential gaming misbehaviors that included cheating, profanity, theft, and hoarding. Because of the pervasiveness of gaming on college campuses as related by Hainey et al. (2011), security personnel must become informed on ways to address the security aspects of potential online gaming misbehavior.

There have also been occurrences of the violation of copyright laws by students, according to Ferullo (2011) who download music, videos, games, and other forms of entertainment as well as examples of copyright violations from professors who misuse intellectual property works. Hemmings (2013) noted that the focus today is more on the expansion of e-commerce, connectivity, and convenience rather than on copyright infringement. Hemmings related that although some attempts to deter copyright infringement by college students has occurred, the practice is still rampant and more

enforcement needs to occur. This means that college information security personnel need to be aware of computing threats related to the specific applications that are being utilized by users and of ways to manage and block illegal content.

Colleges and universities have many facets and operational entities within their organizations and, as such, have a large variety of computing and information systems that may be vulnerable to attack. There have been an abundance of research studies that focused on technology systems used in higher education with associated vulnerabilities that included eLearning systems, wireless systems, cloud computing, web computing, mobile computing, and entertainment-based systems such as gaming and social media. Much of the research that was performed in the varied aspects of computing security in educational information systems underscored the importance and necessity of comprehensive, informed, and well-organized security resources that are commensurate with the size of the institution.

Human Factor Computing Security Risks

Educational information systems are vulnerable to internal and external sources but also are vulnerable to attacks from internal entities that comprise the human factor and the research domain contains many works on risks and solutions. The human factor security risk theme includes the human as the weakest link, the insider threat, phishing vulnerabilities, training and awareness, policy development, and policy enforcement. This literature theme related to the human element of information security recognized the intertwined nature of information systems that contains both human and technological components. The effective management of this intertwined relationship can lead to enhanced security rather than significant vulnerabilities if best practices are followed.

The human factor of information systems as the weakest link is heavily documented in the literature and much attention and research has been dedicated to this topic. The main premise behind the human factor as the weakest link is that even though an organization may have a cutting edge technology-based computing security strategy, the system can still be easily compromised due to the action of a human who may be tricked into clicking a link (Abdul Majid, Abdul Majid, Ibrahim, Wan Manan, & Ramli, 2105; Crossler et al., 2013; Hu et al., 2012; Kearny & Kruger, 2014; Lebek, Uffen, Neumann, Hohler, & Breitner, 2014; Pfleeger & Caputo, 2012; Solic, Nenadic, & Galic, 2012). All of these authors agree that the human is the weakest link in a security strategy but each has a unique perspective or remedy on how to deal with this phenomenon.

The journey through the literature pertaining to the human as the weakest link appropriately begins with a theoretical foundation. Lebek et al. (2014) provided a comprehensive scan of the literature that investigated behavioral motivations into security compliance behaviors from a theoretical perspective. They found that there were 54 theoretical perspectives in use within the literature related to computing security but the most prevalent theories used included the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), General Deterrence Theory (GDT), Protective Motivation Theory (PMT), and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) theory. Insights into the determinants of user intention of security policies was formed by these authors and they found that the main constructs of the TPB were the strongest predictors of security-related behaviors. Hu et al. (2012) also used the TPB in their study and found that it was a significant predictor of the intention to comply with security policies. Posey, Roberts, Lowry, Bennett, and Courtney (2013) utilized PMT to identify protective motivation behaviors (PMB) that are instrumental in

producing beneficial motivation behaviors to deter and prevent security breaches.

Examples of PMB provided by these authors included the report of harmful co-worker behavior or not opening or clicking unexpected links by senders. This underscores the importance of developing security policies that take into account theoretical considerations in order to boost compliance with security best practices.

The human factor security consideration appropriately focused on the human as the cornerstone of modern business and its importance in successful operations. Pfleeger, Sasse, and Furman (2014) found that 35% of all breaches were due to the human factor. Metalidou et al. (2014) argued that attacks on systems are performed by humans and that appropriate defense of systems also occurs by humans. These researchers found that the most significant security issues occur at the point where humans and technology interface and that some of the most successful incursions were related to attacks on the vulnerabilities of humans by use of social engineering. Solic et al. (2012) agree that the social engineering of humans was the most pervasive means that attackers gained access to systems and that phishing schemes were the most dangerous because they allowed attackers to bypass technological defenses. Pfleeger and Caputo (2012) similarly related that only amateur attackers attempt to breach technology but that professional attackers attempt to victimize humans. Pfleeger et al. (2014) also acknowledged the weakness of the human factor but found that certain psychological factors could lead to heroic behavior that foils hacking attempts. This means that most successful attacks involve the use of human deficiencies to bypass technology intended to safeguard systems but that humans can also be an asset if they possess the qualities and training that enable them to recognize and diffuse incidents.

Educational information systems are very much at the mercy of the human factor and computing security initiatives need to make this element an important focus. Abdul Majid et al. (2015) stressed the importance of ensuring that user awareness programs are in place due to attack attempts on systems from users inside the university that occur multiple times each semester. The vigilance they suggested includes careful password management, physical security of devices, and the importance of not sharing any private information with other users. Rupere, Mary, and Zanamwe (2012) agree that users need to be vigilant and suggest that proper training needs to occur to avoid common insecure practices such as not logging out of systems, non-compliance with procedures, password abuse, errors related to input, and sharing of login information for convenience sake. Parsons, McCormac, Butavicius, Pattinson, and Jerram (2013) also offered human factor behaviors that need to be avoided that included risk-taking factors such as attaching unauthorized media to work computers, clicking on embedded links, being tricked into clicking on phishing links in email, or allowing others to discover login information. All of these human factor behaviors highlight the need to ensure that users understand the importance of secure system practices and the need to be aware of potential vulnerabilities.

The literature placed a distinction between intentional and unintentional human factor security behaviors. Crossler et al. (2013) highlighted this difference and explained that intentional behavior includes theft, espionage, and sabotage while those that are accidental include poor password choices, browsing to personal websites at work, placing confidential information in inappropriate places, or inadvertently clicking a harmful link. Rupere et al. (2012) also discussed the difference between intentional and unintentional

behavior and enumerated intentional behaviors as purposeful changes to computer code, revealing confidential system information to competitors, theft of identities, cracking of passwords, keylogging, and phishing activities. They noted that these two types of harmful human activities need to be addressed differently in training and policies and that different sanctions should be implemented for each violation. This suggests that security personnel need to understand both types of human factor behaviors and that the intentional insider threat requires special consideration and additional resources.

Phishing is a specific type of human factor security behavior and there is an abundance of literature that focused on both its detrimental effects as well as ways to mitigate it. Phishing is a way to trick users into divulging sensitive information so that this information can be used for some dark purpose (Kirlappos & Sasse, 2012). Phishing is based on the actual process of fishing where bait is thrown into the water in an attempt to lure an unsuspecting victim to the hook according to Purkait (2012). Lee and Lee (2012) found that phishing schemes were one of the most prominent threats on the Internet and an increase in phishing email to a domain often promotes feelings of insecurity from users of that domain. Kirlappos and Sasse agree that the probability of encountering phishing schemes on the Internet is very high but that these phishing sites come and go so quickly that it is almost impossible to defend against them. Kearney and Kruger (2014) actually performed phishing tests within an organization to determine the percentage of users who would succumb and found that 83% of users fell victim to a phishing test and 64% of these users later fell victim to a follow-up test. The test results by Kearney and Kruger also indicated that 69% of users who fell victim to the first test had successfully completed security training and 92% of users who had previously

completed security training fell victim to the follow-up phishing test. This underscores the importance of understanding how easy it is for users to fall victim to phishing schemes even in the knowledge that those who have received security training fall victim at rates similar to those who have not had training.

The literature has ample information related to the insider threat which is a close cousin to the human factor. Typically the human factor relates to unintentional harmful security behavior but the insider literature also describes intentional harmful security behavior. McBride, Carter, and Warkington (2012) believe that insider abuse is one of the greatest threats to an organization's information security. They referenced a study in which 52% of respondents to a survey acknowledged that incurred breaches were due to the abuse of systems by insiders and 52% of respondents in another survey indicated that they were able to circumvent security controls in their organizations. Willison and Warkentin (2013) agree that negative insider behavior poses one of the greatest threats to information security and noted that many of these attacks are motivated by revenge, rationalization, criminal intent, greed, or complex psychological factors that must be considered by security personnel in deterrence strategies. McBride et al. agree that psychological factors need to be considered and that the design of security initiatives should be based on these factors which may include conscientiousness, openness to new ideas, extraversion, neuroticism, and agreeableness. This suggests that personality factors can be a significant predictor of insider threat and that they be considered in the hiring of employees and the creation of security training programs.

The formation, implementation, and enforcement of information security policies garnered a lot of attention by researchers in the literature and many insights into their

development are available. Chen, Ramamurthy, and Wen (2013) explained that the reason employees do not adhere to security policies is because they are creatures of habit and resist organizational changes. Vance, Siponen, and Pahnla mirrored these sentiments in their 2012 study that found that previous habits and actions without thinking play a major role in an employee's decision to comply with policy. Darcy, Herath, and Shoss (2014) offered similar reasons for non-compliance with security policies including stress-related reasons, inconvenience, and excessive workload. These authors noted that security policies can be perceived as over-burdensome and, because they change and evolve frequently, it is difficult for employees to keep up with them. They even go so far as to suggest that too many and too restrictive policies can have the opposite effect and generate rebellious behavior due to frustration with policies.

There are many approaches to encouraging compliance with security policies and the available research has a variety of advice on compliance strategies. Siponen and Vance (2014) related that it is important for organizations to do more than merely promoting awareness to policies but must also give supporting rationale. Darcy and Devaraj (2012) focused on predictors of technology misuse and explained that informal sanctions for non-compliance may have a stronger impact on compliance than formal sanctions. These researchers noted that factors such as morality and social approval positively impact compliance. Siponen, Mahmood, and Pahnla (2014) also studied non-compliance factors and found that severity of threats, self-efficacy in compliance, attitude toward compliance, social norms, and intention to comply all significantly impacted compliance. The authors of this study, therefore, recommended that the critical nature of compliance be communicated to employees along with appropriate training and

education. Chen et al. (2013) advocated for a combination of rewards and punishment to gain the most significant positive impact on security compliance. Knapp and Ferrante (2012) insisted that it is important to consider both awareness initiatives as well as enforcement to advance compliance in organizations. Finally, Alhogial, and Mizra recommended an holistic culture change in their 2014 study that involved utilizing change management principles and implementation of a comprehensive framework to guide the formation and change of culture. The research demonstrated that, though there are differing insights on how to obtain employee compliance with information security policies, it is a critical component of a security strategy and requires a substantial time commitment and resources to implement.

Compliance with information security policies was found to be a critical component to an information security strategy and most researchers agreed that some sort of training and education initiative is vital to the success of a security strategy. A common approach to information security endorsed by Burns, Roberts, Posey, Bennett, and Courtney (2015) was that organizations need to utilize a comprehensive, packaged approach that consists of security education, training and awareness. These authors recommended this holistic approach to information security because it acknowledges the increased access to information resources in modern organizations and recognizes that employees can positively or negatively impact security. Olusegun and Ithnin (2013) agree about the essential nature of education and advocate for a sustainable approach to the education of employees. They argued that a balance to information security is necessary that stresses both productivity and security and that multiple forms of training is the ideal which may include guest speakers, web-based training, individualized

training, security campaigns, and topical presentations to specific groups.

However, Caputo, Pfleeger, Freeman, and Johnson (2014), like Kearney and Kruger (2014), were interested in the effectiveness of training programs and implemented security tests related to phishing schemes to ascertain the effectiveness of training programs. They found that many training programs were ineffective because employees did not read or comprehend training materials, many participants click before they think, and those that clicked on phishing email were likely to continue clicking on these links. This suggests that training programs need to be carefully created and that phishing training provides easy to understand and in depth explanations.

The research concerned with the human factor acknowledged the importance of managing the intertwined relationship between technology and humans but stressed the human as the weakest link. A great amount of research exists regarding the vulnerability of systems pertaining to the human element of information systems. There is also substantial theoretical foundations that support practitioners in their quest for understanding optimal approaches to the formulation of an information security strategy. Insider negative and positive behaviors were studied to underscore the importance of comprehending the psychological factors that lead to both types of behavior so that policies can be developed in accord with this knowledge. Finally, optimal methods of training and compliance with policy were considered as well as their effectiveness so that organizations can utilize the most effective ways to create a culture of information security.

Information Security Strategies

It is important to consider the theme of existing information security strategies

utilized by organizations to protect their information systems so that insights can be gained on how these can be applied in the educational context. An important first step is understanding how to assess whether the security that is in place is adequate and if enough resources have been invested to ensure appropriate protections. The literature contained a sufficient amount of research that focused on security strategies and the associated incremental components that comprise them including assessment of security implementations, investment recommendations, insights on innovations, and investment in cyber insurance as a means to spread the risk among businesses and to protect the bottom line from unforeseen events. This section reviews the available work related to security strategies and present best practices, insights, strategies, and other aspects of overall computing strategies that are important to the protection of information assets.

One of the most fundamental aspects of a security strategy is the evaluation of the effectiveness and maturity of the currently implemented solution. The International Standards Organization (ISO) created the ISO 27001-27007 standard series to provide a common information security certification framework that can be utilized by businesses to prove that their systems meet the very strict guidelines (Gillies, 2011). This standard was built on previous standards and represents an up-to-date cyclical model that allows organizations to continually monitor the health of their information security implementations and to make improvements if needed (Gillies, 2011). This standard is the most popular security standard available, however, Mbowe, Zlotnikova, Msanjila, and Oreku (2014) noted that other security threat assessment standards exist including Common Criteria, Coras, Octave, TMT, and CySeMol. However, each of these has a unique perspective and approach and are designed for specific types of businesses.

Though the ISO27000 series has been an effective information security guideline for organizations, it is not without problems. Ahmad, Sahib, and Azuwa (2014) found that, though the ISO27001 standard provided a comprehensive list of critical security controls that need to be implemented to ensure information security, the cyclical nature of the model was counter-intuitive because it did not provide a systematic way to measure the effectiveness of the controls. This prompted these researchers to develop a framework, Technical Security Metric (TSM), which would allow this measurement to occur in an organized manner. Gillies (2011) also took issue with the vanilla ISO27001 because it seems to have been developed for large businesses with deep pockets. As a result, he adapted it to construct a model to enable smaller businesses to utilize a modified version of this model. As such, his security model, the Five Stages to Information Security (5S2IS), provides small businesses with a scaled model of the ISO 27001 standard so that SMEs can measure the maturity of their security solutions in a cyclical fashion to ensure risk reduction. Similarly, Mijnhardt, Baars, and Spruit (2016) recognized that the ISO 27001 standard was not practical for SMEs and was too complex and costly for them to implement. They also created a model, Characterizing Organizations Information Security for SMEs (CHOISS), which allows SMEs to tailor the information security matrix to the needs of their organization because of the recognition that no one size security solution fits all and that larger organizations have radically different needs than SMEs.

The importance of assessment of the security implementation cannot be underestimated because most companies invest sizable amounts of resources in this area and want to be sure that the investment is actually affording them protection. As such,

assessment of the implemented security solution was examined by Ahmad et al. (2014) where they stressed the importance of being able to measure the effectiveness of security controls to allow for their effective management. These researchers developed a metric measurement tool that encompasses the ability to determine if institutional security objectives are being met, allows quantifiable data in their effectiveness, provides simple measurement and comprehension, provides a comparable result, provides the ability for timely corrective action, provides a target stakeholder responsible for improvement, provides an improvement in security, and is aligned with business goals. Gillies (2011) agrees that measureable and intuitive metrics are important with his development of a metric tool that spans the breath of the ISO 27001 standard but allows easy understanding of the measured results of his metric model. The work done by these researchers underscored the important nature of implementing a metric model so that the effectiveness of security controls can be objectively judged.

Another assessment strategy that often accompanies an information security metric model consists of employing objective third parties to periodically audit the security control implementation. Steinbart, Raschke, Dal, and Gilla (2012) explained the importance of having a third party feedback mechanism that assesses the effectiveness of implemented controls. However, these researchers noted that these two functions do not always operate together effectively and conflict and tension can occur that limits the effectiveness of this process. Rahimian, Bajaj, and Bradley (2016) also examined the effectiveness of the internal audit of security controls and found that it was beneficial for this function to be provided with an intuitive model that provides a systematic approach to assessment. This approach, according to these researchers, provides an automated way

to assess data security along multiple dimensions which allows for the production of quantitative data that can be easily interpreted. Steinbart, Raschke, Dal, and Gilla also performed a 2013 study in which they more deeply analyzed the relationship between the information security function and the audit function and found that the relationship was positively affected by the information security personnel perception that the audit function was knowledgeable about security controls as well as the perception that the audit function was beneficial to the organization. This means that Information Security personnel were more positive about the process when they felt they were dealing with knowledgeable auditors who they felt were performing a valuable function.

There was an abundance of solutions and strategies available in the research domain that consisted of a potpourri of perspectives related to enhancing information security. Many of these strategies were focused on a holistic view of combatting many threats simultaneously and others were focused on solutions to one of the most pervasive and difficult to defend threat of phishing. Choras, Kozik, Bruna, and Yautsiukhin (2015) subscribed to a more fundamental approach that sought to define a research agenda in terms of priorities by breaking the cyber-security domain into four categories consisting of technical, human, organizational, and regulatory dimensions. These researchers suggested that the top technical priorities in cyber security research include authentication, security testing, malware, and advanced persistent threats; top priority human dimension topics include awareness and education; organizational priorities consist of cultural adaptation to the new normal in institutional security; and regulatory priorities focus on investigatory and forensics topics.

Many organizations are focused on comprehensive network security solutions that

are technical in nature. Stanciu (2013) recommended the implementation of network intrusion detection systems (NIDS) and network intrusion prevention systems (NIPS) where NIDS are designed to detect an intrusion and NIPS are designed to prevent intrusions. Stanciu concluded that because there are so many new and developing threats that it is impossible for human beings to understand all of the risks and to effectively combat threats on their own. Therefore, he believes it is necessary to employ automated solutions to protect an organization's information assets. Aijaz, Aslam, and Khalid (2015) agree with Stanciu that these systems are important but they argued that these protection systems are too disparate and difficult to coordinate. These researchers believe that a more sophisticated and comprehensive system is necessary to combat the modern persistent threats and that a security operations center (SOC) system is necessary to centrally manage and monitor systems, provide customized reporting with incident support, and provide sophisticated analysis of incidents to support forensics activities. The authors noted that without a comprehensive tool, response to incidents is too slow and disconnected to be beneficial to an organization. This suggests that older strategies that lack integration can only be moderately successful due to the lack of a coordinated perspective.

Other cyber security researcher approaches focused on a single, high priority aspect of information security such as authentication. Arutyunov (2012) examined five categories of authentication and control to information systems that includes identification, screening, auditing, cryptographic access, and access control. This author recommended a solution that fits into the budget and culture of the organization which may include biometrics, a user's global positioning coordinates, access tokens, multi-

factor authentication, digital certificates, passwords, or a combination of these. Hussein, Sani, Mahmud, and Abdullah (2013) argued that many modern authentication systems are not reliable and a combination of human and technical solutions are necessary to provide secure authentication and ensure that ensuing transactions are safe from interception and impersonation. These authors proposed a multi-factor authentication model that begins with a username and password but proceeds to a generated one-time password from a registered mobile device. This model used two of the three fundamental authentication factors consisting of something the user knows and something the user has. Ogini related in his 2013 study that biometrics is the most secure form of authentication which utilizes the physical characteristics of a user that may include finger print, hand geometry iris scan, facial recognition, or behavioral characteristics such as key strokes or voice recognition. According to Ogini, all of these methods have advantages and disadvantages but the most inexpensive and easiest to use and implement is the finger printing solution which has greatly improved over the years.

Many other researchers focused on one of the most difficult aspects of security to defend, phishing, which targets the weakest link in a security strategy, the human. Sanchez and Duan (2012) advocated for a sender analysis approach that flags email as suspicious if the actual sender in the Internet protocol stream is different than the organization that it claims to represent. The authors indicated a success rate of up to 98% in the detection of phishing emails using this method. Barraclough, Hossain, Tahir, Sexton, and Aslam explained in their 2013 study that many anti-phishing mechanisms are ineffective and in particular those that depend on blacklists. They developed a neural network that utilizes fuzzy logic based on five input tables in real time that represent all

known phishing strategies without the false positives of other detection methods.

Archchilage and Love (2013) developed a framework for mitigating phishing attacks using a game-based educational strategy to promote avoidance behavior. The researchers found that there are particular elements that should be included in the game design for the highest rate of effectiveness that includes self-efficacy, perception of threat, perception of severity, cost, effectiveness, and the perception of components that are at risk. However, Aggarwal, Rajadesingan, and Kumaraguru (2013) asserted that the number of phishing attacks using email is shrinking and shifting to Twitter which has many dark advantages that disguise the perpetrator. The authors explained that phishing on Twitter is extremely difficult to detect because of the rapid dissemination of phishing links in the Twitter network, the small content size, and the technique that can be utilized to disguise the identity of the sender using a shortened universal resource locator (URL). These researchers have created an extension to the Chrome browser that allows a 92% detection rate in the Twitter application but the user must access Twitter via the Chrome browser for detection to be successful. This approach to detect phishing in the popular application of Twitter is an attempt to keep up with the latest phishing trends and provide a measure of safety in a medium that can be very intense with rapid propagation.

There are still other strategies of enhancing security that focus on holistic approaches to computing security within an organization. Soomro, Shah, and Ahmed in a 2016 study evaluated many organizational factors and found that awareness training, implementation of security policies, compliance training, effective information technology management, effective infrastructure and architecture, alignment of strategy with business objectives, and effective human resource management all significantly

impacted the security implementation. This holistic view of security, according to the authors, represents a shift of responsibility from the information technology department to all of management within the organization. Aleem, Wakefield, and Button (2013) advocated a convergent information security strategy where information technology security personnel and physical security personnel work together as a single converged unit to maximize the effectiveness of security. These authors noted that there is much crossover of incidents and that the talents of both groups would be most beneficial in a converged model. Mathew, in a 2012 study, developed a strategy that addressed the security of an eLearning system. His intent was to create a blueprint for a secure implementation for this type of system which considers the many vulnerabilities that are well-articulated in the literature. In addition to making sure his solution addressed the wide-spread security concerns of eLearning systems, he also solicited the opinions of faculty and students to ensure that the system could still be used effectively.

A final approach found in the literature discussed the notion that there is no way to secure an information system. Bambauer (2014) explained that even though the most sophisticated defensive systems are in place and that users have undergone extensive training, there is no way to defend every aspect of an information system because very well-funded and sophisticated players can attack and breach systems. His philosophy was to divide and differ systems in an organization so that if one system is compromised, all of the systems are not compromised. This heterogeneous approach disperses systems and makes it more difficult to compromise an entire organization. This novel approach suggests that organizations concede that systems will be breached and that they instead focus on mitigation, recovery, and continuity of operations.

The final aspect of information security strategy that is present in the research domain is related to financial considerations and how much to invest in computing security. The investment in computing security initiatives is a difficult item to justify because it is hard to place a value on the benefit gained and also because it diverts precious funds from other endeavors (Stewart, 2012). Kofal and Patterson (2013) agree that security investment decisions are difficult and related that most security investment decisions are made by a small number of individuals in isolation which does not constitute the best way to decide on investment strategies. Fielder, Panaousis, Malacaria, Hankin, and Smeraldi (2016) explained that most surveyed chief information security officers lament the lack of funding as one of the great barriers to effective security. These researchers also point out that SMEs are severely handicapped because of very limited funding for security purposes.

Fielder et al. (2016) examined the most effective investments in cyber-security and found that patch management, firewalls, anti-malware, and secure configurations represented the most cost-effective investments and that only diminishing returns exist for more sophisticated controls. Stewart (2012) noted that most companies invest three to six percent of their information technology budget on security. However, he believes that it is not rational to invest in security solutions in which the benefits cannot be measured or justified. Kofal and Patterson (2013) agree that it is important to find an optimal investment strategy that is based on rational justification rather than fear of the unknown and they believe that the amount invested should be based on the customer's negative reaction to breach events and the willingness of other similar firms to cooperate with each other to strengthen security. The consensus of these authors was to find an investment

strategy that can be linked to associated benefits while taking market factors and competitor actions into consideration.

The final aspect of cyber-security strategies related to the topic of study focused on spreading the risk with some form of cyber-insurance. Young, Lopez, Rice, Ramsey, and McTasney (2016) related that the acquisition of cyber-insurance as a means to keep the investment in cyber-security expenditures in check is a viable complement to existing strategy. Shackelford (2012) also related the importance of protecting the bottom line and noted that the average breach could cost in excess of six million dollars. He also noted that courts are increasingly cracking down on businesses that do not properly care for private information. Young et al. believe that the cyber insurance market has matured due to widely publicized data breaches and that it can now effectively spread the risk and become a valuable component to a cyber security policy. These authors also noted the effectiveness of a cyber-insurance strategy in the face of limited budgets that many SMEs experience. Moreover, the addition of cyber-insurance can be a viable alternative for businesses now that the cost has stabilized and may be best suited for those businesses with limited resources.

The information security strategies that exist in the literature touch on a variety of topics that begin with the importance of being able to assess and measure the effectiveness of security strategy. The research domain has a wide range of information on various solutions and strategies to employ in order to enhance security and minimize risk. Many of these strategies focused on combatting the greatest risk such as phishing while others advocated for more balanced and holistic approaches that attempted to consider all vulnerabilities. Finally, investment strategies were considered that attempted

to determine an appropriate amount to dedicate to computing security that were based on a justifiable analysis. Cyber-insurance was also discussed as an investment strategy for organizations with limited resources and as a viable component of a security strategy.

Impediments to Computing Security in Higher Education

There was representation in the literature pertaining to information security impediments in higher education but in order for the characteristics of small and private higher education obstacles to be evaluated, a broader consideration of the security obstacles faced by SMEs was necessary because they have similar characteristics to small educational institutions. The evaluation of these two characteristics in sum provided a clear representation of the obstacles faced by small and private educational institutions. This final theme contained a fair representation of works that spoke poignantly to inherent characteristics in educational institutions that ran contrary to effective security. Additionally, the broader inclusion of SME characteristics which mirrored small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. helped to complete the true picture of what is faced by security personnel at these institutions.

It is important to note that the first theme discussed in this review of the literature which examined vulnerabilities to educational information systems also contained some elements that could be construed as obstacles specific to higher education such as those that relate to student-centered vulnerabilities. These student-centered vulnerabilities are not present in most other organization types so it is appropriate to classify these as obstacles to higher education in this work. Some of these obstacles included online entertainment sites that would be prohibited in most organizations but must be allowed in institutions of higher education because the market place dictates that students be given

these extra considerations in recognition that their residence halls are also considered their homes. These elements were discussed sufficiently in the first theme and will not be discussed again outside of this paragraph.

Institutions of higher education in the U.S. have many long-standing traditions and philosophical operating principles that may run contrary to best practices in the implementation of security controls. A report published by Reichman et al. in 2014 offered a report to the academic community regarding the possible infringement of academic freedom and openness by new technologies and accompanying methodologies. Some of these problematic infringements include the use of third party cloud services providers that store university information, mobile technology restrictions, required logins for searching public materials in the library, restrictions to social media usage, lack of open access to materials, restriction of materials that may be seen as obscene or harmful, and introduction of filters to electronic resources. These authors related that it is the responsibility of academic leadership, as manifested in a shared governance model, to ensure that new technologies do not infringe upon the sacred principles of academic freedom.

The protestations of Reichman et al. (2014) are shared by Ellern, Hitch, and Stoffan (2105) who vehemently protested the imposition of logins that were not anonymous in a higher education library facility. These researchers were concerned that computing security policies instituted by I.T. that required logins at their library ran contrary to academic freedom and privacy which caused them to perform a study to investigate other institutions to ascertain their policies. They found that most other institutions required logins due to potential vulnerabilities, potential misuse of resources

and lack of control of their resources which ran contrary to their hypothesis. Kam and Katerattanakul (2014) referred to academic freedom as the “cornerstone of higher education in the U.S.” and that it runs contrary to properly implemented security controls (p. 29). These researchers found that academic personnel would only institute security policies that were in harmony with academic freedom and would directly refuse to implement those controls that ran contrary to them. Ayyagrai and Tyks (2012) also related that academic freedom runs counter to information security and notes that academic freedom is a “deeply held value” (p. 86) that requires careful navigation. This suggests that the academic freedom principle is held as a fundamental and overarching principle by many which trumps all other policies that may impede information security in the academic setting.

The Kam and Katteral (2014) study was based on a germinal study performed by the Educause researcher, Kvavik, who performed a 2004 study that surveyed the landscape of higher education to determine impediments to the implementation of security controls at institutions of higher education. While some of the findings of this study are outdated, many are still relevant which include issues such as the need for awareness and education campaigns as well as participation of management in the creation of a culture of security. The findings included a list of the most important barriers to the implementation of information security controls that include lack of resources, lack of awareness, academic freedom, decentralized culture and systems, absence of policies, enforcement of policies, and lack of senior management support. These findings indicate that the top priorities over a decade ago are still largely relevant today.

Many works underscored the notion that institutions of higher education were vulnerable to attacks and that they could even be considered a top target. Arlitsch and Edelman (2014) asserted that higher education organizations are among the top targets in the world and that approximately 100,000 attempts to hack the University of Wisconsin's systems are encountered on a daily basis by China itself. They also noted that data breaches have grown exponentially and are estimated to have grown to 717 since 2005 in institutions of higher education. Ayyagrai and Tyks (2012) agree that institutions of higher education are particularly at risk and indicated that since 2005 that approximately 21% of data breaches happen in these institutions. These authors presented an example of a disastrous breach of data at an institution of higher education and explained how the attacker penetrated the system and extracted personal information. This means that educational institutions are not only experiencing hack attempts but are also experiencing actual incursions into their systems which underscores the importance of appropriate security controls.

There are many reasons that educational institutions are vulnerable and targeted which may represent a crisis within these organizations. Song (2012) explained that higher education institutions only spend minimal time on security measures because personnel have many responsibilities and that security is often the lowest priority. In addition, he noted that the skillsets in these institutions are lacking and resources for professional development in this area are also lacking. Kam and Katterattanakul (2014) cited the principles of academic freedom and openness as barriers as did Ayyagrai and Tyks (2012) and Arlitsch and Edelman (2014). Holter and Seganish (2014) indicated that the adoption of online learning has brought many layers of risk as well as the emergence

of other technologies that have been implemented without proper consideration of security. Miseviciene et al. (2012) agrees that online learning is a security liability but also asserted that lack of budget, antiquated systems, and poor security strategies are also at issue. Hodgman (2014) argued that financial pressures have led to many challenges at universities and that deferred I.T. spending and maintenance is a common result. Holter & Seganish (2014) concur that cost reduction initiatives have been a very important consideration for these institutions because of the limited resources dedicated to information technology which has necessitated their strategic allocation in order to cope with budget reductions without compromising the quality of their systems. Arlitsch and Edelman related that the large number of computing devices and robust bandwidth also plays a role in attractiveness of these institutions to hackers. Reichman (2014) conceded that the research environment which focuses on learning, collaboration, and sharing of information can have security ramifications as well. Finally, Vinay (2013) indicated that a combination of technological and human behaviors are factors including students making contact with strangers on the Internet, lax security habits, sharing login information, and not keeping antivirus software up to date.

All of these factors in aggregate not only put institutions at risk for attack and breach, but also present a monumental challenge for security personnel at these institutions because these barriers to effective computing security are made up of a variety of elements that require careful navigation. The most challenging of these barriers include the changing of culture to eliminate lax security and political considerations such as the faculty beliefs of the sacredness of academic freedom.

The recognition that there are barriers to the successful implementation of

computing security in higher education is referenced in the literature but the number of works that describe this phenomenon are few. Song (2012) articulated that the barriers to information security exist in institutions of higher education and that they need to be understood in order for adequate information security to be implemented. He conceded that the barriers are different in each institution but that they need to be addressed and eliminated if these institutions are to make progress. The germinal study performed by Kvavik in 2004 also recognized these barriers and produced a lengthy list of them using data from a survey sent to 435 college and university administrators. The study by Kam and Katerattanakul (2014) is one of the few recent studies that addressed these barriers and argued that these barriers may not be able to be overcome from within but, instead, may take a variety of forces from within and outside the institution to pressure the organization for change. This means that I.T. leaders may be faced with a challenge that is not entirely in their power to change and that it may take other forces to aid in the change process.

The other aspect of the obstacles to computing security theme focused on the unique challenges of small and private higher educational institutions which was investigated by considering SME computing security concerns. The SME topic was utilized in order to fully understand the specific impediments of the small college relative to its size because characteristics of SMEs mirror those of small and private institutions of higher education. The small and private higher educational institution represented the sample of interest in this study and the impediments related to size were examined in this section. The consensus of research suggested that though SMEs represent the backbone of the economy, they are at risk due to a lack of focus on information security. These

SME institutions have many of the same challenges as small and private educational institutions and their perspectives, issues, and solutions are well-represented in the literature.

SMEs have not been targets of attack in the past but recent research indicated that this trend is changing. Minjhardt, Baars, and Spruit (2016) related that 18% of SMEs encountered some form of online attack each year. Paulsen (2016) indicated that 43% of the 2016 phishing attacks were aimed at SMEs which is an increase of 9% since 2014. Paulsen noted that even though SMEs are now considered a target by hackers, only half of SMEs believe that there is a significant risk of attack on their businesses. Hayes and Gilmore-Allen (2015) agrees with Paulsen and explained that even though SMEs are more easily compromised, the leaders of these businesses still underestimate the risk of attack. Bougaardt and Kyobe (2011) also concur that SME executives underestimate the risks to their businesses and that often untrained and unskilled workers are responsible for information systems and their security. This indicates that SMEs do not fully understand the risks to their systems and that this lack of understanding contributes to their attractiveness as targets.

A lack of understanding is one factor that contributes to the attractiveness of SMEs as a target but there many others. Paulsen (2016) enumerated factors such as the lack of legal pursuit from SME attacks, low visibility, high vulnerability, and effectiveness as a launching pad for larger targets. Hayes and Bodhani (2013) argued that SMEs normally have plenty of assets that are worth the effort of attack and that they are the perfect training ground for attacks against larger targets. Gilmore-Allen (2015) indicated that SMEs are susceptible to attack because their information can be leveraged

at higher levels of attacks and fraudulent schemes without being detected as quickly. These factors underscored the importance that SMEs become educated about the risks and to put measures in place to adequately protect their assets.

A breach for an SME can be devastating and may ultimately lead to the company ceasing operations. Paulsen (2016) explained that SMEs have a lot to lose by not securing their information systems. He noted that even a small attack or breach of information can cripple a company or drive it out of business. Paulsen also indicated that breaches of an SME can poison a sector of business because consumers may lose confidence and not engage with that business or similar businesses due to lack of trust in their systems. Gilmore-Allen (2015) agrees and referred to it as a matter of survival for SMEs because the average loss of 5% of revenues for a data breach to an SME can be devastating and many SMEs cannot recover from that type of a loss. Moreover, SMEs have a greater risk to attack than larger corporations but they are the least equipped to handle such an event.

Many of the problems faced by SMEs related to a lack of security controls originate from multiple factors. Sangani, Vijayakumar, and Pilani (2012) explained how larger organizations have the ability to invest suitable resources in computing security strategies but SMEs do not possess the level of resources necessary to apply toward computing security controls and strategies. Bougaardt and Kyobe (2011) noted other factors that SMEs encounter that put their organizations at risk in addition to skillsets, budgetary resources and human resource shortfalls enumerated by Sangani et al. which include management indifference, poor vision, distributed systems, poor risk management experience, and insufficient comprehension of computing security concepts.

Kaur and Mustafa (2013) explained that SMEs are not subject to the same requirements as large organizations related to information security and, as such, are not required to document their information security plans and implementations. These factors in aggregate illustrated the importance that SMEs adapt to changing times because as Paulsen (2016) argued, it is not necessarily the strongest companies that survive, but those that can adapt the quickest.

One of the most intimidating problems for SMEs is trying to understand and implement the security controls that have been created by international standards organizations that seem to be intended for larger businesses with little thought to SMEs. Fielder, Panaousis, Malacaria, Hankin, and Smearaldi (2016) recognized the scarcity of resources that SMEs possess and have developed a model using gaming theory that prioritizes the controls that are the most cost-effective. Minjhardt et al. (2016) likewise understood the level of complexities of security standards such as Cobit and ISO 27001 and developed a model that allows SMEs to simplify the process in easy-to-understand terms and also eliminates those controls that are not applicable. Sangani et al. (2012) took a more fundamental and basic approach by enumerating the most pervasive threats with easy to understand language and then providing practical remedies for these elements. They argued that lack of understanding was the greatest barrier to security and that an understandable explanation would be of the most benefit to SMEs. Coerte and Solms (2013) also provided a simplified set of security controls for SMEs as part of an information security governance toolbox that is designed to not only create a set of security directives, but also contains a means to assess the compliance of efforts to these new directives. Clarke (2015) similarly provided a checklist of absolute minimum

requirements for SMEs so that they would not have to wade through complex documents with many directives that are not applicable to the SME context. Therefore, there is no shortage of information and resources available to SME leaders about how to implement information security controls but there is the challenge of educating and convincing these leaders that it is a priority worthy of their attention and resources.

The research enumerated thus far indicates the importance of leadership and vision in the adoption of SME security priorities. The toolbox of security controls created by Coerte and Solms (2013) utilized a control phase that allows management to assess the level of compliance with implemented security controls. Bhattacharya (2011) also recognized the importance of SME leadership style in the implementation of security controls by studying this relationship. He found that the transactional leadership style is effective in the implementation of security controls but that transformational leaders were better able to garner an increased amount of effectiveness, effort and satisfaction from employees toward information security. Finally, Barlette, Gundolf, and Jaouen (2015) studied the importance of the CEO on the effectiveness of security implementation and effectiveness and found that it was important for them to communicate with employees about the importance of information security and set a good example of positive security behaviors. This was found to be particularly important by these researchers when no chief information officer exists in the organization. Moreover, leadership is not only responsible for recognizing the importance of information security and providing resources, but also for communicating its importance and setting a good example.

The obstacles and barriers to information security discussed in this section were both related to the unique higher education characteristics and also those related to the

characteristics about the size of the organization. Both of these topics were addressed by reviewing literature specific to higher education and by examining works related to SMEs. The cited obstacles specific to education highlighted the unique operational and philosophical elements of educational institutions that make it difficult to implement computing security controls or run contrary to information security initiatives. These factors included academic freedom and openness, shared governance, experiential learning, online learning systems, decentralized operations and systems, the desire to protect privacy and anonymity in research, and fundamental research and collaboration models (Ayyagrai & Tyks, 2012; Hodgman, 2014; Holter & Seganish, 2014; Kam & Katerattanakul, 2014; Kvavik, 2004; Miseviciene et al., 2012; Reichman, 2014; Song, 2012; Vinay, 2013). The SME obstacles that were enumerated in this section included lack of awareness, lack of understanding, lack of resources, lack of dedicated personnel to information security, a small target mentality, lax security habits, lack of leadership, lack of documentation requirements, and limited skillsets (Bougaardt & Kyobe, 2011; Gilmore-Allen, 2015; Hayes & Bodhani, 2013; Kaur and Mustafa, 2013; Paulsen, 2016; Sangani et al., 2012). The sum of the academic and SME obstacles and barriers adequately represent the operating environment of small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. This aggregate set of obstacles was compared and tested with the data that was generated during the analysis phase of this study.

Information Security Theoretical Considerations

Embedded within the works that were discussed above include many theoretical considerations that sought to explain information security circumstances or provided a foundation for models and solutions. Arpaci et al. (2015) utilized the Theory of Planned

Behavior (TPB) to understand the motivations of using a particular technology as well as the perception of its security. Bambauer (2014) used Normal Accident Theory to argue for an approach that consisted of limiting the damage in a breach. Bartolacci et al. (2014) relied upon Routine Activities Theory to explain why students may engage in attacks on other students. The use of the Theory of Crime and the Stage Theory of Loss were employed by Bougaardt and Kyobe (2011) to explain an individual's response to loss and a lack of self-control that led to victimization. General Deterrence Theory was utilized by Knapp and Ferrante (2012) to discuss why employees chose not to comply with security policies. Lee and Lee (2012) highlighted several theories including Subjective Expected Utility Theory, Prospect Theory, and the Theory of Planned Behavior to explain why employees fell victim to phishing schemes as well as why humans are the weakest link in a security strategy. Finally, Purkait (2012) discussed a compromised system due to a phishing attack and related how Protection Motivation Theory helped to explain the influence of this breach on a person's future behavior.

Summary

The various lines of research found in the literature and discussed above included four major themes related to information security within small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. The first theme encompassed threats to educational information systems which can be internal or external and included attacks as well as harassment via computing systems (Spalevic, 2014; Wall, 2013). These vulnerable systems included wireless networks, online learning infrastructure, mobile computing, web-based systems, and cloud-based systems as well as student use of gaming and social media technologies (Al-Ibrahim, 2012; Budhrani & Sridaran, 2015;

Dennen, 2015; Popescul & Georgescu, 2015). The second theme involved the human factor component of information security consisting of both vulnerabilities and remedies. Wall (2013) emphasized that humans were the weakest link in an information security strategy but can also be an asset if properly trained. The third theme from the literature discussed information security strategies that are in use today that either reduce risk or evaluate the effectiveness of information security solutions. The final theme that emerged from a review of the literature was related to the specific impediments present in higher education environments including academic freedom, academic openness, financial pressures to do more with less, limited resources, and a narrow vision related to information security (Arlitsch & Edelman, 2014; Bougaardt & Kyobe, 2011; Holter & Seganish, 2014; Sangani et al., 2012). This final theme also focused on factors related to the size of small and private institutions which include lack of awareness, lack of understanding, lack of resources, lack of dedicated personnel to information security, a small target mentality, lax security habits, lack of leadership, lack of documentation requirements, and limited skillsets (Bougaardt & Kyobe, 2011; Gilmore-Allen, 2015; Hayes & Bodhani, 2013; Kaur and Mustafa, 2013; Paulsen, 2016; Sangani et al., 2012). Finally, theoretical foundations used in the studies that were reviewed included The Theory of Planned Behavior, Normal Accident Theory, Routine Activities Theory, Theory of Crime, Stage Theory of Loss, General Deterrence Theory, Subjective Expected Utility Theory, Prospect Theory, and Protection Motivation Theory. All of these themes in aggregate aided in designing this multi-case study as described in chapter three.

Chapter 3: Research Method

This study focused on the obstacles to information security in small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. and randomly selected and examined eight of these institutions using a multi-case study format. This chapter describes the research plan and methods that were be used in this study and provides detail on how the data was collected and analyzed as well as the context and setting of the study. Following is a restatement of the problem, purpose, and research questions of this study, which will provide a fresh focus on the specific problem being examined.

College and University users expect all campus computing resources and environments to be reliable, fast, safe, ubiquitous, and secure. However, there are limited resources to accomplish those expectations (Stewart, 2012). As a result, technology managers find it extremely challenging to balance stakeholder expectations with information security best practices and must strategically assign precious monetary and human resources to formulate an effective security strategy (Stewart, 2012). If budgetary, philosophical, and strategic higher education mandates must be satisfied along with sound information security, then technology managers must prioritize, innovate, and carefully weigh the benefits and drawbacks of investments in security solutions as well as their impact on the campus community.

The overall business problem that was explored consists of determining and understanding the importance of information security at these small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. Because most small to medium enterprises (SME) do not believe that they are truly at risk due to their belief that their institutions do not represent a desirable target for hackers, too little attention and

resources are devoted to information security (Sangani et al., 2012). Additionally, campus stakeholders are unwilling to compromise their positions on academic freedom, allocation of additional monetary resources, submission of information systems to rigorous security tests, and access to entertainment systems for additional security (Asllani, 2012; Bartolacci et al., 2014; Hodgman, 2014; Kam & Katerattanakul, 2014). The specific business problem that was examined consists of determining the proper priority and allocation of information security resources so that effective solutions and strategies are implemented that balance the needs of stakeholders with information security best practices. A balanced information security approach is necessary because it must take into account the available financial resources of the institution as well as the environment in which it operates (Kam & Katerattanakul, 2014; Knapp & Ferrante, 2012; Sangani et al., 2012).

The purpose of this qualitative, descriptive multi-case study was to examine eight institutions from the population of 1,269 small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. that grant a bachelor's degree and explore the impact that their unique computing requirements and expectations had on the effectiveness of their implementation of information security controls. Information security controls consist of hardware, software, outsourcing and consultative resources, departmental skillsets, and training methodologies for department personnel as well as the entire campus community in relation to their current computing network security implementation. Data was gathered from the randomly selected institutions using semi-structured telephone interviews of personnel responsible for information security to ascertain how the unique operational impediments in the higher education context affect the implemented security

solutions. The interviews attempted to elucidate key indicators, contributing factors, insights, perspectives, and innovations related to the efficacy of implemented information security strategies and controls as well as the perceived effectiveness of the security strategies by users.

- Q1.** Which operational barriers impede small and private, non-profit higher education institutions from implementing information security controls?
- Q2.** Why are current provisions lacking in the ability to maintain information security controls?
- Q3.** What resources are needed to address operational barriers in the implementation of information security controls?

The multi-case study method is described in this chapter along with its appropriateness for this study as well as the logical plan that connects the design to the research questions. The population and sample of the study are discussed in addition to the method used to select the cases. The interview protocol is outlined and the methods used to collect, process and analyze the data are delineated. Finally, assumptions, limitations, delimitations, and ethical assurances are described that define the context and set the boundaries of the study.

Research Methods and Design

A qualitative, descriptive, multi-case study was utilized to study the efficacy of implemented computing security solutions in small, private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. from the perspective of those personnel who are responsible for information and computing security. The case study research method typically answers how and why questions and is ideal to gain a deeper understanding of complex

phenomena rather than only focusing on frequency of occurrence (Yin, 2014). A case study intended to generate insights about a phenomenon rather than the case itself is known as an instrumental case (Stake, 2006). This multi-case study utilized an instrumental case study design that focused on the phenomenon of information security impediments in small and private institutions of higher education.

Case study research involves creating and organizing a study using research questions as a foundation and then interpreting and experiencing a phenomenon in its original habitat related to the research questions using observational techniques to generate a more complete understanding of the phenomenon so that it can be portrayed to others (Stake, 2006). A multi-case study methodology is ideal when conclusions across numerous cases are sought and is stronger than a single case design because multiple cases offer more compelling evidence than a single case (Yin, 2014). Multi-case studies are best with more than three cases but less than ten because too few cases results in limited conclusions that can be identified during multi-case analysis and too many cases results in too much data to process for deeper understanding (Stake, 2006). The number of cases selected for a study should not be analogous to a sample size in a quantitative study but should rather be determined by the strength of the conclusions desired by the researcher and the elimination of rival explanations (Yin, 2014). Therefore, a replicative approach was used that drew on eight randomly selected cases to strengthen the conclusions of the study and eliminate rival explanations. These cases were selected from the total population of small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S.

This design steps of this multi-case study included a logical plan or blueprint to

connect the data that was gathered with the research questions and consisted of the (1) research questions; (2) propositions; (3) units of analysis; (4) the rationale to connect the data to the research questions; and (5) the logic for interpreting the findings (Yin, 2014). Rationale was provided that described each of these research design components in a way that relates them to the themes that emerged from the literature review as well as the research questions. This provided a cohesive framework for the study as well as the necessary details of how the steps proceeded.

The three research questions were restated above and represent the basis and foundation of this research study. The main focus of these questions involves the discovery of operational obstacles and impediments to computing security in these institutions of higher education. The questions not only sought to understand the impediments, but also desired to comprehend why existing solutions were not effective and what measures would be needed for them to be efficacious. The research questions sought to not only discover the what, but more fundamentally wished to discover the why and how of this phenomenon to justify the use of the case study methodology (Yin, 2014).

There were not any formal propositions in this study, however, they were implicitly present in the research questions as well as the review of the literature. The research questions connoted an inability of information security personnel at institutions of higher education to effectively implement information security controls due to philosophical and operational barriers. Also implicit in these questions and the literature review were the pervasive nature of these threats and the high level of risk for not complying with security best practices. The focus of the study on small and private

institutions of higher education also propagated the idea of lack of appropriate human and financial resources in small organizations. Finally, the works uncovered in the review of the literature supported these implied propositions as well as the salience of the research questions and provided a firm foundation for this study.

The case study research method has typically focused on individual cases as the unit of analysis, however, modern case studies may focus on topics, institutions, groups, ideas, programs, etc. (Yin, 2014). This multi-case study focused on small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. that grant at least a bachelor's degree. These institutions represented the unit of analysis as the target for analysis of the operational barriers for the implementation of information security controls within these organizations. This analysis was conducted using a semi-structured interview of the personnel responsible for the implementation of information security controls within these institutions.

The rationale used for connecting the collected data to the research questions and propositions involved an overview of the actual steps of the analysis of the data (Yin, 2014). The researcher analyzed the data collected across the eight case studies using a comparative methodology that focused on replication to strengthen conclusions of the study and eliminating rival explanations (Yin, 2014). The interviewed data was coded and then pattern-matched along with a synthesis that spanned the cases in order to provide explanations and answers to the questions. This comparative synthesis and the derived explanations were used to support the research questions as well as the implicit propositions.

The interpretation of the results of the study did not involve a statistical approach

as found in quantitative study but, rather, focused on the elimination of rival explanations (Yin, 2014). This approach supported the use of a higher number of cases that approaches the high limit of ten as suggested by Stake (2006). This means that the decision to select eight cases represented the desire of the researcher to strengthen the conclusions of the study by utilizing multiple case support. This approach helped to eliminate rival explanations for the impediments of effective computing security controls that included (1) inappropriately created controls that do not support academic institution unique aspects of freedom and openness; (2) an evolved vision that suggests that computing security is a low priority; (3) there are not enough resources available to support the high costs of security controls; (4) inadequate security measures available to secure educational technologies; or (5) security strategies do not support student entertainment expectations. This enumeration of rival explanations as part of the design of the study further aided the researcher during the data collection phase to ensure that the data collected addressed these issues.

The case study research design was effective in accomplishing the study goals because the researcher sought to understand the practical aspects of the challenges faced by institutional security managers with this complex phenomenon (Yin, 2014). This could not be accomplished with a mere quantitative statistical analysis because that type of analysis could not reveal the struggles, insights, and daily undocumented problems that arise. A semi-structured interview of information security personnel elicited a deeper and thicker description of the challenges faced by security personnel and also provided their perspective on potential solutions. Moreover, this case study allowed the researcher to probe deeper into the information security implementation by asking how and why

questions that allowed the participants to openly provide their perspectives and experiences.

Population

The population of the study included the 1,269 small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. with less than 5,000 on-campus students that grant at least a bachelor's degree (IPEDS, 2016). The intent of the researcher was to focus on those institutions that were both bound by the traditional and philosophical traditions of higher education as elicited in the review of the literature but to also include those small institutions that faced the further challenges of lack of resources, lack of understanding, and lack of leadership (Bougaardt & Kyobe, 2011; Holter & Seganish, 2014; Kam & Katerattanakul, 2014; Sangani et al., 2012). The researcher also sought to focus on private, non-profit institutions because these institutions typically have limited financial resources and are strongly dependent on tuition for operational success (Hodgman, 2014). These characteristics in sum pose a challenge to the implementation of information security best practices and represent the desired characteristics to respond to the problem and purpose of this study.

Sample

The case study research methodology is best served when more than two cases are selected and less than ten because too few cases may produce bias and weak results but too many cases lead to an overabundance of information that cannot be effectively analyzed (Stake, 2006). It is also important to understand that the case study research methodology sample size cannot be likened to a justified sample size in quantitative analysis because it is not a valid comparison (Yin, 2014). Rather the selection of the

number of cases is at the discretion of the researcher and his/her goals as it leads to the strengthening of conclusions similar to performing an experiment multiple times (Yin, 2014). This replication approach is, therefore, the relevant aspect of the number of cases selected and has caused the researcher to select eight cases which is on the high side of the recommended number of cases to include in a multi-case study. This affirms the researcher's commitment to strong conclusions and the elimination of rival explanations.

The selection of cases was accomplished by downloading into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet the demographic summary data of the 1,269 small and private educational institutions in the U.S. that grant at least a bachelor's degree with less than 5,000 on-campus students (IPEDS, 2016). The alphabetical listing of these institutions were numbered using the "fill data series" function of Excel. The "randbetween" function of Excel was then used to generate 16 random numbers between one and 1,269 that were used to select the institutions based on the filled number that was assigned to each institution. The researcher sent the information technology security leader at each of these institutions an email soliciting participation in this study according to the policies of the Institutional Review Board at Northcentral University. A follow-up phone call was made to enlist and codify the participation of these schools and to answer any questions or concerns. Eight representatives of the institutions agreed to participate in the study but it required two iterations of the randomization process.

Materials/Instruments

The case study protocol represents the instrument component of a case study and provides the study guidelines and procedures, overview, the data collection strategy, the data collection questions, and reporting considerations related to presentation and format

(Yin, 2014). The case study protocol is critical in a multi-case study and increases reliability because it provides a standardized methodology for approaching each case to ensure that there is a valid means of comparison and synthesis (Yin, 2014). This multi-case study adhered to the protocol stated below which represents the collection and presentation strategy of the data.

This study involved the examination of operational impediments in the implementation of information security controls at small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. A multi-case study methodology served as the approach to garner insights, contributing factors, perspectives, and innovations related to the implementation of information security controls at these institutions. The research domain indicated that academic institutions possessed fundamental philosophies and traditions that may run contrary to information security best practices and that small institutions have a lack of resources, understanding, and leadership pertaining to information security (Bougaardt & Kyobe, 2011; Hodgman, 2014; Holter & Seganish, 2014; Kam & Katerattanakul, 2014; Sangani et al., 2012). These characteristics in sum represent a significant challenge faced by personnel responsible for information security within these institutions and comprise the focus of this study.

The data collection strategy for the acquisition of data within the work environment of the participants consisted of semi-structured telephone interviews of personnel responsible for the implementation of information security controls as well as policies and enforcement. Access to participants was solicited via email with a follow-up telephone call to solidify participation. Telephone interviews took place at the convenience of the participant and originated from the office of the researcher who wore

a headset so that his hands were free to enter notes directly into Microsoft Word as a means of documentation of the interview. The researcher understood that it was necessary to deviate from the script in order to let participants provide details that they felt were pertinent. Efforts were made to allow this latitude within the confines of the protocol which seemed to provide deeper understanding and unanticipated insights. Assurances were given to the participant about complete anonymity and privacy of data collected in accordance with the procedures set forth by the internal review board of Northcentral University so that the participant felt comfortable in providing accurate and honest answers to questions.

The generalized lines of questions followed eight themes and the specific questions used are shown in Appendix A. The general line of questions for the participants attempted to understand the obstacles and impediments faced as a result of institutional traditions, philosophies, operational aspects including specific utilized technologies, training considerations, budgetary limitations, political considerations, resource limitations, leadership deficiencies, and student considerations. These lines of questions had their foundation in the literature which suggested that these were elements of concern within these institutions. Data collection goals focused on eliciting which obstacles existed but also sought to understand how and why these obstacles were not overcome and what measures were necessary to overcome them as aligned with the study research questions. Questions were constructed so that the main line of inquiry focused on institutional characteristics rather than the individual's characteristics because the unit of analysis was the institution rather than the individual (Yin, 2014).

It was also necessary to present a preliminary framework for the anticipated report as part of the case study protocol to ensure that it contained the necessary information appropriate to the audience and publication medium (Yin, 2014). The completion of this doctoral study necessitated a thorough synthesis and report of the findings in a manner that embodied a clear understanding of the issues, sufficient evidence of findings, and strong conclusions. The findings for this study were provided in a detailed narrative format that was aligned with the study research questions and goals and provides sufficient evidence for the conclusions based on the data. As such, the researcher presented overview information, information specific to each case, synthesized information, conclusions, and a summary of the entire study from beginning to end. This format provided an understanding of the context of the study, goals, conclusions, and insights garnered.

Data Collection, Processing, and Analysis

The data collection steps of this study were provided for ease of understanding as well as replication purposes. The data was collected from individuals who oversee the information security control implementations at small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. Solicitations for participation were performed in a randomized manner using the “randbetween” function of Microsoft Excel from the 1,269 non-profit institutions that convey at least a bachelor degree and have less than 5,000 on-campus students. A follow-up phone call to the solicitation emails was made to enlist and codify participation from eight institutions.

Data was collected via semi-structured telephone interviews of participants using the questions shown in Appendix A. The researcher performed the interviews from his

office using a hands-free headset and a computer to type in notes from the interviewee. The researcher believed that he would be able to obtain more honest and open answers if he did not record the interviews and provide assurances of anonymity and privacy of the data collected. Data security is considered a sensitive topic and assurances of anonymity were important so that participants believed that no adverse consequences would occur as a result of participation.

The interview data was entered into a Microsoft Word document and later coded using the “comment” feature using a set of a priori codes with flexibility to add emergent codes. The a priori code designations are outlined in Appendix B and consist of three letter representations of anticipated obstacles and impediments that include institutional traditions, philosophies, operational aspects including specific utilized technologies, training considerations, budgetary limitations, political considerations, resource limitations, and leadership deficiencies. The interviewer made use of a Microsoft Word macro that automated a portion of the coding process which extracted comments with codes and placed them into a separate Word document table that were easily copied into Microsoft Excel for analysis.

The analysis of the data in Microsoft Excel consisted of using the data sort option as well as the filtering option to perform pattern matching for comparative analysis. The filter option of Excel enabled the researcher to isolate the data with multiple codes to perform a deep analysis and to draw conclusions across the eight institutions. Additional columns were used to make notes and provide additional comparative subheadings that aided in the building of explanations as well as cross-case analysis. Themes were sought that conformed to the a priori code and emergent code topics in the building of

explanations that responded to the research questions. Insights and perspectives were collected from follow-up questions and additionally volunteered information. Finally, the analysis of data included attempts to refute rival explanations and strengthen the conclusions elicited from the data.

The role of the researcher of a qualitative case study is different than the role of a researcher in a quantitative study. A quantitative researcher strives to perform the study in an objective manner by disappearing from the study whereas the qualitative researcher is regarded as an instrument of data collection and interpretation (Stake, 2006). The researcher role is vital as an instrument of data collection because the researcher is able to ask follow-up and probing questions that lead to valuable insights depending on his/her understanding of the phenomenon and the answers provided by participants (Yin, 2014). This notion suggested that the researcher in this study needed to have a thorough understanding of the topic and be sufficiently conversant on the topic to obtain relevant insights. The researcher also needed to be sufficiently fast at typing to capture the interview notes and be skilled at interpreting the data to recognize patterns, ask pertinent follow-up questions, and develop conclusions.

Assumptions

The assumptions of the researcher related to the total population of institutions were that of a general homogeneity of the organizations pertaining to the services that are delivered and the methods used to deliver them. Academic institutions typically have administrative staff, faculty, and student constituents that are served by some form of instruction in a face-to-face, online, or hybrid format. The homogeneity of these services is evidenced by the ability of credits to generally qualify as transferrable from one

institution to another suggesting a consistent format of production and consumption of educational services. The academic institutions were also assumed to have a computerized network, Internet access, computer servers, and many forms of software applications that store personal and sensitive information that needs to be protected.

The researcher assumed that the responses of study participants were open and honest and that information was provided that addressed the posed questions. The assurances of anonymity were very important to the efficacy of the information provided by participants because of the sensitive nature of information security. The researcher took appropriate steps to not only guarantee the participants of complete anonymity, but ensured that descriptions of the individual cases did not allow for the deduction of their identity. In addition, the researcher provided assurances about the steps taken to secure the data as well as the method of eventual destruction of the data.

Limitations

The main limitation of the study consisted of the sensitivity of the subject matter and the questions being asked. Information security leaders may have been hesitant or unwilling to divulge the true state of their implemented security solutions due to lack of efficacy of the implemented solutions, the fear of adverse consequences, or the fear of releasing information about potential weaknesses of their implemented security solutions (Wahyuni, 2012). This means that data from the potential sample could have contained bias and misleading information that could impact the validity and reliability of the study if adequate assurances of anonymity and privacy were not effectively communicated. Open and honest answers were, therefore, critical to the findings and conclusions of the

study and the participants did present sufficient information to provide an understanding of their impediments and concerns.

The validity and quality of the study were determined by adhering to tactics that increased reliability as well as construct, internal, and external validity (Yin, 2014). Reliability of this multi-case study was enhanced by utilizing an electronic spreadsheet database to carefully document results as well as strict adherence to the protocol to ensure replication. This careful documentation enhances the repeatability of the study by providing detailed procedures and aids in reducing bias and errors (Yin, 2014). Construct validity was enhanced in this study by demonstrating multiple occurrences of evidence using eight cases and a logical progression of evidence. Multiple occurrences and a pattern of evidence were sought because Yin believes that this not only increases the quality of the study but presents a more organized set of measures from which conclusions can be drawn. Internal validity was addressed in this study by performing rigorous analysis of data, which included pattern-matching, the addressing of rival explanations, and providing clear constructs of explanations. A detailed and careful analysis is necessary for enhanced internal validity because it aids in discovery of relationships and conditions that are relevant to the results (Yin, 2014). External validity of the study was addressed by using a sound theoretical foundation that consisted of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Organizational Learning Theory (OLT) as well as utilizing a replication approach to the study. This approach provides more generalizable results because it ensures that the data collection strategy addresses the research questions and is applicable to the theoretical foundation of the study (Yin, 2014).

Delimitations

The researcher decided to focus the study on a subset of institutions of higher education that only included small and private, non-profit organizations that grant at least a bachelor's degree. A small institution is defined in this study as having less than 5,000 on-campus students. It was not advantageous to include all students in the smallness calculation because many of these institutions are branching out into online education as well as graduate programs to fund the on-campus experience. Additionally, for-profit institutions were not desired in the scope of the study due to their general ability to attract investors, which runs contrary to the traditional model of higher education. The researcher was not interested in publicly funded community colleges so the distinction of "private" was added as well as the delimiting factor of existing as a four year bachelor degree granting institution. The implementation of the delimiting characteristics was accomplished using the Integrated Postsecondary Education System (IPEDS) website, which allowed for the download of this information based on intuitive selection criteria.

Ethical Assurances

It was important that this research be performed ethically because research that is administered in an unethical manner results in a waste of time and money and contributes to invalid results that may cause distrust of research and researchers (Committee on Science, 2009). It is essential that researchers understand that ethics are applicable to every phase of the research study and that improperly designed studies could adversely affect the results and credibility of the study as well as the research discipline along with the potential to cause harm to participants (Wester, 2011). It is also essential to properly care for data with appropriate measures of security and privacy along with careful

consideration of storage and preservation of data which results in higher quality and validity of the study (Mutula, 2011). All of these issues had adequate attention so that the study results had higher validity and so that participant rights were properly taken into consideration.

The Belmont report was created in 1979 as a summarization of the National Research Act that was passed in 1974 as a result of violations of human rights in research as well as subsequent committee deliberations and specifies three principles that must be adhered to that include respect for the human person, beneficence and justice (Belmont, 1979). This report highlights respect for the human person as a recognition of their right to participate in study or not participate in a study as well as protection for those who do not have full autonomy; beneficence as the right of persons to be treated ethically with respect for their decisions; and justice as the equitable distribution of deserved benefits. This study adhered to all directives in this report and the informed consent form that was developed reflects all standards of care for participants as shown in Appendix D.

Informed consent is a procedure documenting the scope and risks of the study in an understandable format so that participants can provide permission to take part in the study according to the terms of the form (APA, 2010). The American Psychological Association (APA) sets forth informed consent guidelines with consideration for those who do not have the ability to provide consent, rights of participants, proper disclosure of risks, and clear procedures to document participant consent. The informed consent guidelines were created for the protection of study participants who may have not been properly informed in the past which caused undue harm and suffering (Wester, 2011).

An informed consent form was created by the researcher that outlined all study risks along with the nature and procedures of participant interaction as shown in Appendix D. This form also provided detail on how the data will be collected, cared for, and destroyed. This form was emailed to potential participants so that they could fully understand the scope of the study and their role before they consented to participation. The participants then emailed the signed form back to the researcher before the interview and collection of data occurred. The data was secured, as outlined in Appendix D, by ensuring that the data will be kept behind two locked doors in a safe. The research computer hard drive was encrypted so that the data cannot be accessed even if it is stolen. The data will be kept for seven years and then the electronic data will be deleted and the paper data destroyed per the mandates of the Internal Review Board (IRB) at Northcentral University.

IRB approval requirements from Northcentral University were set forth in the Dissertation Resource Manual and have jurisdiction on all studies that utilize human participants and are conducted in conjunction with employees of North Central University (NCU, 2016). These IRB requirements were mandatory to ensure the protection and safety of participants as well as to reduce the risk of the study so that data was collected in an ethical manner. The IRB requirements ensured that participation in the study was completely voluntary, study participants were insulated from harm, the study was intended to obtain knowledge, the study was operated in a just manner, commitments to all involved in the research were honored, and participant rights were guaranteed (NCU, 2016).

The researcher was compelled to obtain the IRB application form from the

Dissertation Center and forwarded the completed application to the dissertation chair which included the Collaborative Institutional Training certificate for approval (NCU, 2015). The study documentation that pertains to the IRB form was consolidated and submitted so that the approved form was sent to the Doctoral Tracking System by the dissertation committee chair (NCU, 2016). After the IRB application was approved, the approval date was sent to the committee chair and the student which indicated that data collection may begin (NCU, 2016). It was essential to understand that data collection could not occur until IRB approval was granted and that any violation of this tenet could result in dismissal from the program (NCU, 2016).

Summary

This study focused on the obstacles to information security in small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. and examined eight of these institutions using a multi-case study format. College and University users expect all campus computing resources and environments to be reliable, fast, safe, ubiquitous, and secure with only limited resources to accomplish those expectations (Stewart, 2012). As a result, technology managers find it extremely challenging to balance stakeholder expectations with information security best practices and must strategically assign precious monetary and human resources to formulate an effective security strategy (Stewart, 2012).

Data was gathered from the eight randomly selected institutions using semi-structured telephone interviews of information security officers to ascertain how the unique operational impediments in the higher education context affect the implemented security solutions. The general line of questions for the participants consisted of questions that sought to understand the obstacles and impediments faced as a result of

institutional traditions, philosophies, operational aspects including specific utilized technologies, training considerations, budgetary limitations, political considerations, resource limitations, and leadership deficiencies. The analysis of the data in Microsoft Excel consisted of pattern matching for comparative analysis, building of explanations, and cross-case analysis, which enabled the researcher to perform a deep analysis and to draw conclusions across the eight institutions. Themes were sought that conformed to the topics that emerged from a review of the literature which aided in the building of explanations that responded to the research questions.

The design steps of this multi-case study included a logical plan or blueprint to connect the gathered data with the research questions and consisted of the (1) research questions; (2) propositions; (3) units of analysis; (4) the rationale to connect the data to the research questions; and (5) the logic for interpreting the findings (Yin, 2014). This approach helped to eliminate rival explanations for the impediments of effective computing security controls that may include (1) inappropriately created controls that do not support academic freedom and openness; (2) prioritization of resources that do not hold computing security as a top priority; (3) employment of a cost/benefit strategy by leadership that cannot justify high costs of security controls; (4) inadequate security measures available that secure the pedagogical technologies; or (5) inadequately employed security strategies that allow for full access to entertainment sites.

Limitations of the study consisted of the fact that information security leaders may have been hesitant or unwilling to divulge the true state of their implemented security solutions due to lack of efficacy of the implemented solutions, the fear of adverse consequences, or the fear of releasing information about potential weaknesses of

their implemented security solutions (Wahyuni, 2012). The validity and quality of the study was enhanced by adhering to tactics that increased reliability as well as construct, internal, and external validity (Yin, 2014).

Ethical issues were also important to the validity and quality of this study and informed consent was obtained from study participants. An informed consent form was created by the researcher for participants that outlined all study risks along with the nature and procedures of participant interaction. Internal review board (IRB) approval requirements from Northcentral University are set forth in the Dissertation Resource Manual and have jurisdiction on all studies that utilize human participants and are conducted in conjunction with employees of North Central University (NCU, 2016). It was important to understand that data collection could not occur until IRB approval was granted and that any violation of this tenet could result in dismissal from the program (NCU, 2016). The methods outlined in this chapter were strictly adhered to in order to provide reliable and valid findings that are described in chapter four.

Chapter 4: Findings

This qualitative, multi-case study examined computing security at eight institutions from the population of 1,269 small and private, non-profit institutions of higher education in the U.S. that grant a bachelor's degree and explored the impact that their unique computing requirements and expectations had on the effectiveness of their implementation of information security controls. Data was gathered from the randomly selected institutions using semi-structured telephone interviews of personnel responsible for information security to ascertain how the unique operational impediments in the higher education context affected their implemented security solutions. The interviews were used to answer fundamental questions that sought to understand the barriers to the implementation of efficacious information security controls as well as what institutional resources were lacking and what resources would be necessary for the optimal implementation of these solutions.

This chapter outlines the findings of the semi-structured interviews of information security personnel at the selected institutions. First, an overview of the entire interview process has been given to provide context for the collection of data as well as an understanding of the process. Second, a security context summary of each of the eight institutions has been given to provide a foundational illustration of the respective cases. Third, a detailed analysis is presented that includes an overview of the interview questions, a cross-case analysis, synthesis, strategies, insights, and innovations. Finally, an evaluation of the findings is presented that correlates with the literature review, responds to the research questions, provides a refutation of rival explanations, offers a linkage to the theoretical foundation, and delivers an interpretation of the results.

Results

The collection of data consisted of interviewing the personnel responsible for information and computing security at eight randomly selected small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. All of the study participants were leaders of the IT operation who were also responsible for information security. The goal was to interview the leaders responsible for computing security rather than an actual security officer for two reasons. First, few of these institutions have a dedicated security resource and second, leadership tends to have a holistic view of the IT operation, the computing security status, and the overall institution itself. The participants were requested to use a secure location for the interview so that no eavesdropping could occur. To promote more open dialogue, the interviews were not recorded because I believed that participants would be more comfortable and candid if I were only taking notes due to the sensitive nature of the topic. The participants agreed to take part in the confidential and anonymous interview by providing responses as opinion rather than as authorized representatives of the institution. This requirement by the Northcentral University Internal Review Board seems to have resulted in more candid and open answers by the participants. All interviews were performed within two weeks of each other and I used the same question format and protocol while allowing latitude in responses and conversation. All identifying information was removed from the interview notes including institution type (i.e., college or university) as well as the gender of the participant (i.e., he or she) to reduce the likelihood that an institution could be deduced. Institutions will be referred to, for example, as “institution A” or “institution B” and the

participants will be referred to as “the leader.” A brief summary of each of the institutions follows and contextual information security status is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2
Information Security Status by Institution

Institution Designation	Security Rating	Major Breach	Cyber Insurance	Dedicated Resource	Security Framework
A	7	No	No	½	No
B	6	No	No	½	Yes
C	5	No	No	No	No
D	7	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
E	6	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
F	3	No	No	No	Yes
G	4	No	No	No	No
H	6	No	Yes	Yes	No

Institution A. The IT security leader at this organization had a very keen sense of the importance of computing security and also has a very good understanding of sound information security practices. Even though the institution did have a half time person dedicated to IT security, they were not very far along in the implementation of formal controls. The organization had been fortunate to have good IT staff skillsets and senior leadership that realized the importance of computing security and was willing to allocate the necessary resources toward it when a need was identified and justified. This leader had been successful in collaborating with the state-sponsored computing consortium in higher education and had taken advantage of their programs, resources, and knowledge. There had been a small amount of conflict with faculty in the administering of computing controls, and the leader believed that it was possible that more would occur as more controls were implemented. However, the faculty model at this institution was less traditional so that they understood the need for security policies and procedures. The human factor aspect of their information security program seemed to be weak with no

formalized user education in place, but plans were underway. The leader gave the institution a high security rating (seven on a scale of 1-10), has had no significant breaches in the last five years, had no cyber-insurance, had a half-time person dedicated to computing security, and did not use a formal security framework.

Institution B. This IT leader was somewhat knowledgeable about computing security and the application of controls at the institution but there was an apparent element of frustration that focused on lack of human resources, lack of budget, lack of leadership vision, lack of leadership priority, lack of leadership importance, and inability to convince leadership of importance and priority. This leader emphasized that the lack of progress on the implementation of security controls was primarily due to lack of resources. The leader felt fortunate to develop security skills in the existing IT staff that enabled them to keep the security measures of the organization “afloat” without any significant breaches. The leader underscored the fact that the IT staff had excellent skills and was knowledgeable, but they are by no means sufficient. It was evident that the institution was not that far along with computing security when the leader indicated that they were only beginning to consider a formalized security model such as the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) controls. The leader gave the institution a medium security rating (six on a scale of 1-10), has had no major breaches in the last five years, had no cyber-insurance, had a half-time person dedicated to computing security, and was using the NIST control framework.

Institution C. The leader at this institution was very thoughtful about computing security but clearly did not have knowledge of all the possible threat vectors. The leader indicated that there was not sufficient time, considering the rest of the IT duties, to delve

into the details of what it would take to secure the institution. The leader knew that a Computing Information Security Officer (CISO) would have the necessary time and would understand what would be needed but their organization could not afford another resource and the leader did not believe that the resource would have enough to do. The leader had not taken the time to get additional computing security education for staff members as it had not been determined to be a priority. The security vision and priority had not been communicated to senior leadership, and there had not been any conflict with the academic side of the institution due to lack of progress in the implementation of security controls. A lack of resources for basic IT functions seemed to have pushed security issues to a lower priority. The leader gave the institution a medium security rating (five on a scale of 1-10), has had no significant breaches in the last five years, did not know if they have cyber-insurance, had no person dedicated to computing security, and did not use a formal security framework.

Institution D. The IT security leader at this institution was extremely knowledgeable and confident about their approach to computing security. The leader lauded quality IT staff with great skillsets that had implemented some very good security solutions. The leader admitted to dereliction in a computing awareness and training program on the user side but is taking steps to begin improvements such as removal of administrative rights from workstations and an initiative that tests their users on how well they recognize phishing attacks. The leader did not believe in the efficaciousness of a formalized user training program but instead advocated for testing to improve performance and understanding by users. This leader seemed to have a solid computing security foundation and was also drawing on a formalized security framework for

guidance as well as drawing on others' knowledge and experience. The leader understood the limitations of the institutional budget but maximized the value and benefit of investments in security initiatives. The strongest component of this leader's security strategy was the excellent IT staff skillsets as well as the leader's vision and ability to collaborate with others to draw and share knowledge. The leader gave the institution a high security rating (seven on a scale of 1-10), has had a moderate breach in the last five years, had cyber-insurance, had no person dedicated to computing security, and used guidance from several security frameworks.

Institution E. The leader at this institution was very conscientious about computing security and had an excellent understanding of its magnitude and extensiveness. The leader has had some security training and understands which issues are a high priority. The leader had collaborated with other area institutions in the state to perform vulnerability assessments that addressed computing security requirements mandated by the state. However, the leader related that users at the institution believe that security was an IT problem and was working to shift that mentality with some success by implementing mandated annual awareness training and putting into place a computing security committee. The leader worked diligently to communicate the security vision to senior leadership team through the use of graphics and assessment results. The leader understood that computing security needed to be more of a priority but was severely limited by a lack of resources and staff time to focus on it. The leader regretted that IT security was done primarily when there was spare time instead of regularly and systematically. The leader believed in a clear security vision and strategy and desired to engage in more collaborative efforts with other institutions and share

resources, knowledge and experiences. The leader gave the institution a medium security rating (six on a scale of 1-10), has had no significant breaches in the last five years, had cyber-insurance, had no person dedicated to computing security, and was using the Sans.org security controls framework.

Institution F. The leader at this organization seemed to be very knowledgeable about computing security and had been using formalized computing security frameworks for guidance in security strategy. A perceived low opinion of the security efficacy of the organization compared to other institutions may be indicative of an IT leader that more thoroughly understands the many and varied vulnerabilities of the institution. This institution had very good IT staff and skillsets, according to the leader, but there was not enough of them to go around nor was there sufficient budgetary resources to properly implement controls. Funding was an enormous challenge with this institution. The leader believed in using technology to secure the campus and was making more and more progress every year with a goal of implementing dual factor authentication. This campus has had an ongoing conflict with faculty over the implementation of security controls which they believed ran contrary to academic freedom, tradition, and openness. The leader gave the institution a low security rating (three on a scale of 1-10), has had no significant breaches in the last five years, had no cyber-insurance, had no person dedicated to computing security, and was using guidance from the NIST and Information Technology Infrastructure Library (ITIL) security frameworks.

Institution G. This leader was very thoughtful about computing security but clearly was not very far along in the implementation of sound security controls. The lack of a formalized computing security framework, lack of resources, lack of priority, lack of

password policy, lack of a training program, and the extreme lack of commitment by leadership may have been indicative of an overall failure in computing security. There had also been clashes with academic personnel over computing security initiatives and the leader feared that additional restrictions would lead to further conflict. New institutional leadership had just been put in place which had given the leader hope that more support would be forthcoming for computing security. The overall feel from this leader was that not only was there little to no funding for computing security, but there was not enough funding for the other core services that IT offers. Overall, the leader was very unsure of the vulnerabilities to the institution and seemed to have an inadequate implementation of computing security controls other than basic perimeter defenses. The leader gave the institution a medium security rating (four on a scale of 1-10), has had no significant breaches in the last five years, was not sure if they have cyber-insurance, had no person dedicated to computing security, and did not use a formal security framework.

Institution H. This leader was particularly optimistic about computing security at the institution and seemed to be knowledgeable about the many varied aspects of computing security. Though there were no dedicated security resources on staff and no formal security control framework had been adopted, they had been able to accomplish a fair amount of technological security solutions with existing IT staff. Budget and IT human resources were very tight at this small institution but a breach scare in the last year helped to raise awareness and enabled some dollars to be available. The leader had been faced with a substandard pay scale and did not believe that a dedicated security resource could be justified and hired but was open to sharing a human resource with other institutions. The institution had been able to implement network access control, an

advanced firewall, an automated log scanning tool, an advanced security system service, and an alerting utility which has had positive results in identifying and reducing incidents. The institution had encountered resistance from academic and administrative users but had been able to work through some of those conflicts to garner support. The leader believed that the end user aspect of computing security was their source of greatest risk but only provided informal training on a periodic basis. The leader had recently created and implemented a security incident response plan which should be valuable in the event of a breach. The leader gave the institution a medium security rating (six on a scale of 1-10), has had no significant breaches in the last five years, had cyber-insurance, had no person dedicated to computing security, and did not use a formal security framework.

Analysis. The analysis of a multi-case study includes an examination of both the individual cases as well as the cases in aggregate and considers the research themes, phenomenon, issues, singularities and commonalities that connect the cases together (Stake, 2006). The researcher studies the cases and creates thematic codes, observation notes, and rankings of both prominence and utility to provide a framework for analysis (Stake, 2006). Microsoft Word and Excel were used to extract coded comments from the interview dialogue which were sorted by code and then institution to aid in the creation of thematic notes. These coded and sorted comments were then further coded in additional spreadsheet columns by research theme, research question applicability, and importance to the study. Additionally, atypical results were coded so that these individual anomalies could be reported and balanced with the findings. This coding methodology provided the ability to utilize the Excel sort and filter commands to report the comments by code,

theme, research question relevance, individuality, and priority as seen in Table 3. This functionality was instrumental in conducting the cross-case analysis, the triangulation of evidence, the merging of findings and the generation of assertions. The logical layout of this analysis consists of an overview of the interview questions, a cross-case analysis and synthesis, and a review of insights, strategies and innovations at the institutions.

Table 3
Sample Coded Data

Pg-Ln	Comment	Code	Inst	Notes	Them	RQ	Atyp	Pri
4-1	When it comes to security, they get what is requested.	BUD	A	Has moderate budget by using existing IT dollars.	3	3	A	H
6-5	There is never enough time and money for computing security.	BUD	A		4	1		
2-19	Beginning training. Time, money, and human resources are the biggest obstacle to getting training in place.	BUD	B	Severe budgetary limitations	4	1		
3-4	Major budgetary limitations. Time and money are the biggest hindrances to security.	BUD	B	Major budget limitations	4	1		
4-20	Money, time, staffing are biggest issues along with staff resistance to change.	BUD	B		4	1		
5-15	Two people needed, 500k	BUD	B	Would take 2 people & \$500k	3	3		
5-17	VPN for remote desktop access. Budgetary issues. MS SFTP didn't require additional hardware. Mac people can't use SFTP so can't VPN in.	BUD	C		3	1		

The interview questions were designed around three groups. The first category consisted of impediments that emerged from a review of the literature and consisted of institutional traditions, institutional philosophies, operational aspects, specific technologies, human factor issues, budgetary limitations, political considerations, human

resource limitations, leadership deficiencies, student factors, and entertainment factors. The second category included questions about what had been successful and what had not been successful. The final category focused on insights, innovations, cautions, resources, and vision. Additionally, several questions were answered as a part of each interview that provided information security context. The questions in aggregate were designed to answer the research questions, provide information linking actual practice to the themes that emerged from the review of the literature, and provide a clear picture of the state of information security at each institution with thick descriptions.

The study participants seemed to be knowledgeable about the current status of computing security at their respective institutions and were able to provide responses to the questions that enabled me to gain a good understanding of their status. The range of computing security expertise, however, varied across a continuum from very knowledgeable at institutions D, E, F, and H, to a medium amount of knowledge at institution A, to very little security knowledge at institutions B, C and G. All of the participants were very open to the questions, and none seemed reluctant to share information even though their response may not have shed a positive light on themselves or the institution.

The most common theme across all of the institutions was a lack of adequate budgetary resources and staff to adequately address security concerns. The unanimity of this theme vehemently underscored the magnitude of how this impediment constrained security control implementations. Institution C remarked that there really was not sufficient budgetary resources for any IT initiative much less computing security. Institution B cited significant budgetary limitations as the biggest obstacle for security

initiatives and training. All of the institutions reported that their IT budgets were used for computing security initiatives which resulted in a prioritization of initiatives. Institution D was more advanced than the rest of the institutions because the leader had been able to allocate a significant amount of resources from the IT budget to use for security initiatives. However, this leader lamented the lack of a dedicated computing security line item and that security initiatives compete with other IT initiatives for completion.

Institution B, E, and F seemed to be the most frustrated and panicked about the lack of budget and resources. Institution B complained that money was the biggest hindrance to computing security, institution E noted that it understands what needs to be done but that projects break down when money is needed, and institution F believed that they were just keeping things “afloat” with no money to improve. Institution G noted that it would take a breach for senior leadership to make funds available. However, institution H recently had a breach scare that turned out to be benign, but the leader explained that the incident raised awareness with senior leadership and some funds were made available for security in the aftermath. A summary of responses related to the budget theme is shown in Table 4.

Staffing was the second most voiced impediment and was in unanimity with all institutions complaining about lack of staff and time to address security initiatives. Institutions A and B both had a half-time employee dedicated to computing security but the resource at A was just approved and was shared between two institutions. The leader at A was concerned with trust issues with this new employee and was not sure how the person would fit in the departmental and organizational structure. The half-time resource

at B was shared between networking and security, and the leader confessed that most of the resource's time was spent on networking. All of the other institutions addressed security initiatives with existing IT staff as time allowed.

Table 4
Budgetary Impediment Response Summary

Institution	Responses
A	There is never enough time and money for computing security.
B	They have major budgetary limitations. Time and money are the biggest hindrances to security.
C	There is not adequate budget for anything and computer refreshes have been challenges.
D	They can generally do what they need to do. They can fund a decent level of security out of the IT budget and enough staff to support it.
E	Budget and time are the limiting factors for them.
F	Financially, it is very difficult. IT has an operational budget only and there have been no budget increases. They believe everything is getting more expensive and their budget is not increasing.
G	They believe it would take a breach to actually get funding because their administration does not see this as a priority.
H	They had one scare last year which was benign but it raised security awareness. This scare helped to release funds which got them a better firewall.

Institution B was very adamant that the lack of a security employee and insufficient time of other IT human resources for computing security were responsible for their poor security status. The leader at B went so far as to say that lack of time was responsible for the leader's inability to even investigate security controls and make them a priority. The leader at A believed a dedicated security resource was necessary and would enable the institution to maintain a focus on computing security. The leaders at C, D, and F noted that their existing IT employees have good security skillsets and G explained that their model is that everyone does everything. The leaders at E and G believed that a dedicated security human resource at their institution was not possible due to their low pay scale as well as the existence of other high priority projects at the college, so they were growing a resource by investing in training for existing IT

resources. They believed this strategy was the only viable way to obtain the proper skills, but acknowledged that it would take a long time to develop the desired skillsets. There was also the possibility that the resource in whom they've invested could leave the institution. A summary of responses related to the staffing theme is shown in Table 5.

Table 5
Staffing Impediment Response Summary

Institution	Responses
A	One half person is shared between networks & security.
B	One half security employee is shared between two institutions.
C	A new person would be desired but they are not sure if they could justify that with other needs. Finding someone at that level and salary would be incredibly difficult.
D	They would like additional staff and tools but they feel fortunate to have great people with great skillsets.
E	They would like additional staff but are not confident it is going to happen given current needs. A person dedicated to awareness would free up people to work on other security initiatives.
F	They had a consultant come in to do a staffing analysis. They were found to be understaffed. They feel they need more people.
G	Their IT staff model is that everyone does everything. They do not even have someone dedicated to networks.
H	They have struggled to raise pay rates. Some positions they cannot find people to fill because the pay scale is so low. Security is in such demand that they do not think they could afford anyone.

Another concern shared by the leaders of these institutions was related to the academic side of the organization. Some of these leaders had already weathered battles with faculty where security initiatives ran counter to academic philosophies of freedom, openness, and long-standing traditions. The leader at institution A recalled that a vulnerability scanning tool that they had been using for ten years on their network was recently discovered by faculty members. This discovery resulted in a protracted conflict where faculty members accused IT of spying on them. Institution C had witnessed faculty sharing login credentials with student workers in violation of policy for some time now but has been unwilling to confront them to avoid conflict. Though C had not had

many instances of faculty conflict, they believed that further stringent controls could instigate them.

Institution F had seen many violations of security policies because faculty members believe that many of the security policies conflict with their mission. As a result, the leader had chosen to pick battles carefully and fight for higher priority items and let lesser items slide. Institution F lamented that because faculty would not tolerate the removal of administrative rights from their computers, it caused IT a lot more work because they had to wipe and clean workstations when they became infected. This institution had been unable to institute a password policy, local area network (LAN) policy, or an authentication policy. These policies were attempted but the faculty senate opposed the initiatives which led to a failed implementation.

Institution H had also fought with faculty and finally compromised with them on the implementation of a password policy that required less frequent changes than IT desired. The leader at H was happy with the compromise but admitted that it had been extremely difficult to get faculty to respect security policies, which had led to a give and take relationship to enable progress. One of the most explosive battles with faculty at H was over the implementation of a 15-minute inactivity timeout on classroom computers. Though faculty were vocal and complained about this perceived annoyance, they eventually accepted the change. The leader at D has had many similar experiences with faculty, but strong senior leadership and support from the Provost enabled them to take servers away from faculty so that IT could securely administrate them. The servers had all been hacked over time, but faculty still insisted on retaining control. Though the

leader at D won the server battle, the faculty had successfully resisted attempts to remove administrative rights from their office machines.

Institution E has had some issues with faculty over the many new and “shiny” technologies that have proliferated the campus. It had been impossible to test all of these technologies and faculty have had no qualms using them even though they may put the organization at risk. Institution B acknowledged that their faculty has expectations of total openness which prevented them from blocking applications on the network or computers. Moreover, leaders at B, C, E, F and H, all admitted that more stringent security controls would lead to further conflict with the academic side of the institution which had resulted in an unwillingness to implement additional controls because of a reluctance to antagonize a politically powerful group at their institutions. A summary of responses related to the academic theme is shown in Table 6.

Table 6
Academic Impediment Response Summary

Institution	Responses
A	They had a conflict with faculty because the software inventory scanning tool was discovered by them and they accused IT of spying on them.
B	So far security measures have not caused conflict with faculty. However, future measures could conflict.
C	Faculty are blatantly sharing usernames and passwords with student workers.
D	IT now runs all servers but five years ago that was not the case. All of the academic servers were hacked so IT now runs them.
E	There has been a proliferation of technologies and there are too many to test. Faculty constantly want to implement something new.
F	There is no password policy, LAN policy, or authentication policy. The faculty senate was involved and battled the measure because they never had to do it at other schools.
G	They were blocking a eastern European area. Academic personnel were corresponding to eastern European colleagues and they forced IT to unblock it.
H	Faculty gave in and now are changing passwords. They are not changing them as frequently as IT would like, but it is better than it was.

In addition to evidence of academic and faculty impediments to computing security at these organizations, there were also political issues that had to be taken into consideration by the IT leaders. The leader at A remarked that there was no power to coerce senior leadership to comply with security initiatives and that if they do not choose to obey them, there was nothing the leader could do. Leader B acknowledged that there were politics in play with users and some users were more receptive to security policies than others.

This leader believed that there will be more contention now that there was a half-time security resource in place who would undoubtedly introduce more security controls. Leader C admitted to senior leadership politics where some of these leaders openly violated policies by sharing login credentials with assistants. Leader D did not think there were political security impediments present at the institution but believed there soon would be as more controls were implemented. Leader F had not seen many political issues yet, and G was fearful of implementing controls due to the belief that there would be resistance. H acknowledged political concerns and cited the example of an administrator who requested an account which would not require the password to be changed.

Leadership and comprehension impediments were also evident at these institutions, and it was apparent at institution B where leadership had made it clear that they did not want anything implemented that would cause complaints. The leader at B believed that little progress would occur because there was no one at the senior level to advocate for change. The leader at C lamented poor communication with the President and senior leadership and heard a rumor that the President may be involved in a

computing security initiative. This leader, however, had not placed a high priority on computing security and had not made an effort to articulate concerns to senior leadership. Institution D had not seen any leadership issues but believed there eventually would be issues when additional controls were attempted. Leader E admitted that their security implementation was not coordinated and had no systematic plan. This leader had attempted to convince senior leadership about projects but they broke down when significant dollars were needed. The leader at G complained about lack of senior leadership support and a high level of resistance by them concerning computing security initiatives. Senior leadership had historically seen computing security as a low priority at their institution but the leader was hopeful for change now that the CFO and President had recently been replaced. Leader H also indicated that upper management was fairly supportive of security initiatives but when these projects required additional budget, there was resistance.

The leaders at A and F reported supportive senior leadership who had made financial resources available for security projects. Leader A explained that senior leadership understood and supported projects and that the COO was a good ally and advocate. This leader gave frequent security updates to the senior leadership group and the President was active and involved. Additionally, Leader A related that board members were also becoming involved with security and were asking questions about a security framework. Leader F likewise indicated a supportive leadership team that provided additional resources when a convincing justification was given. This leader noted that many of the leaders had previous experience with computing security at previous institutions and were supportive even though institutional resources were scarce.

The supportive teams at A and F were in stark contrast to Leader G who believed it would take a breach to make resources available. A summary of responses related to the leadership and political theme is shown in Table 7.

Table 7
Leadership and Political Impediment Response Summary

Institution	Responses
A	Senior leadership understands security measures. The COO is a good ally and will help lead. If senior leadership doesn't choose to do it, the leader cannot stop them.
B	There is not a lot of political drive to get security in place. Senior leadership doesn't want anything where users will complain.
C	The leader believes there are much higher priorities than computing security. The President might be involved in some security initiative.
D	There are not too many leadership issues yet but they haven't pushed it yet. There may be issues when required security practices are implemented.
E	Leadership assumes IT is dealing with security. The campus assumes IT is anticipating problems. There is a pervasive feeling that it belongs to IT.
F	Leadership is supportive of security policies. Leadership has experience with other schools and are bought in.
G	There is no support from the former VP of finance and President. There is a lack of understanding and security is a low priority with them.
H	Upper management is fairly supportive. There is pushback on budget. One of the VPs requested the same password and to never have to change it.

There was evidence of computing security comprehension issues at the IT leadership level as well as at the user level. The leader at D believed the institution was a small target and, therefore, had a lower level of risk. Users at institution E believed that security was the problem of the IT department and were more concerned with other issues. At institution F, the new IT leader remarked that the previous administrator made decisions about technology implementation that ran contrary to good computing security. The leader at F also believed that users do not comprehend the level of vulnerability and were too trusting. The leader at H admitted to not knowing what they do not know which suggested a lack of comprehension. The leader at E also has had difficulty understanding how to attack computing security and was not sure where to begin. Leader B may also have comprehension issues because of the low priority that had been assigned to it and

because of the inability to devote time to security education and comprehension. A summary of responses related to the comprehension theme is shown in Table 8.

Table 8
Comprehension Impediment Response Summary

Institution	Responses
A	There are not using a framework yet and are still evaluating which one would be best. They are still trying to figure out what Department of Education letter means.
B	They believe this is a lower priority than other IT issues.
C	The IT leader believes there are much higher priorities than computing security. The leader heard that President may be involved in some security initiative.
D	The leader is not sure where to begin.
E	The campus thinks that information security is an IT issue or someone else's problem.
F	The leader believes it is difficult to change people's mindset. Their users don't realize the scope of the data they have and the vulnerability.
G	They did not have support from the former VP of Finance and President. There was a lack of understanding and security is a low priority with them.
H	They do not believe there is a real need. They don't know what they don't know.

There were also indications of technological impediments of required operational technologies. Institution A acknowledged network vulnerabilities but felt there was not much that could be done due to their satellite locations all over the world. This leader also commented on third-party technology vendors who practiced unsafe computing practices. Leader B mentioned the belief that the cloud seemed to be the most challenging technology to secure because of the lack of control. Leader C noted that, upon arrival as the IT leader, there existed many consumer-grade wireless access points that had to be eliminated in favor of a centralized commercial wireless system. This leader also explained that virtual private network (VPN) access had been inconvenient for users due to low funding which required utilization of a technology that did not support Macintosh systems.

The leader at D highlighted the issue where a workstation technology was put into place to control access to the network, but it had to be abandoned because of lack of IT human resources to manage it. The leaders at E and G noted that hacking threats had led them to block certain parts of the globe. The leader at E blocked a part of the world that required certain international students on campus to use cell phone hotspots to access resources from their home country. Leader G related the incident where a European geographic area was blocked, but a faculty member later succeeded in having this blockage revoked so that collaboration could continue to occur with a colleague in that geographical location. Leader G also indicated that some of their technologies required an element of trust because Apple TVs could easily be commandeered by students if they desired. Institution G was also concerned about the new push for online learning at the organization and the security ramifications that would undoubtedly occur.

Almost all of the leaders related that wireless access was a challenge for them and that measures had been taken that included upgrading wireless systems and segregating wireless networks away from the network used by administrative personnel. Many of the leaders regretted that they had open and unfettered wireless access to accommodate the campus community and visitors. Leader G complained about the proliferation of consumer-grade technologies on campus such as Apple TVs and Amazon Connect devices, and leader E noted that there was such a proliferation of new technologies and devices on campus that it was impossible to secure them all. A summary of responses related to the technology theme is shown in Table 9.

There were numerous human factor security concerns at these organizations and there were indications that user acceptance and support was a challenge. The users at B

were used to getting their way, which caused difficulties in the implementation of security controls due to the belief that security is a burden which inhibits productivity. Institution C gave examples of users sharing login credentials at every level of the organization. The users at E believed that security was someone else's problem and the leader at this institution referred to users as lazy and likely to take the easiest route. Many users at G did not pay attention to warning emails from IT and some were compromised as a result. The users at H were described as too trusting and not suspicious enough of potential security concerns.

Table 9
Technology Impediment Response Summary

Institution	Responses
A	If the institution has struggled, it has been with third party partner technologies not being secure as possible.
B	The cloud seems to be the technology where there is the most risk because it is not totally in the control of the institution.
C	When leader arrived, there were consumer grade access point routers, Linksys, Netgear, and a 3Com router. These had pre-shared keys and they do not function well.
D	There is open WIFI and they have users and guests without passwords.
E	There is open guest access to wireless. There are too many technologies to test.
F	They do a wireless survey every year to try to improve access. Guest access is too easily accessible.
G	The Apple TVs could be a threat. Students could commandeer an apple TV which means their strategy is based on trust.
H	Wireless is a pain in the neck for them and not very secure.

Surprisingly, none of the institutions had implemented a formalized user training or awareness program for users other than E but the IT leader at this organization had to periodically remind the Human Resources department to send out the reminders to users to complete the program. Institution H admitted that their resource's time was spent on networking. All of the other institutions addressed training for users once each year during the summer and would like to do some test phishing of their users. Institution G relied only on warning emails sent to users from the helpdesk but saw the need for a more

formalized training program especially with new users who seemed to be easily compromised. Institution F had no formalized training program in place, and G did summer workshops along with warning emails. The leader at C did not have any formalized programs but had considered some training initiatives based on a calendar that was mailed to the institution that had suggested topics for each month. Institution B was just beginning training, and A sent out emails as part of security awareness month. The leader at A was planning on implementing a formalized program and may use a security video training program from Sans.org.

All of the leaders understood that phishing was the greatest threat to their users but institution C and F believed that users at their institutions were savvy enough not to click on a phishing link. Institution D related that several users at the institution were compromised by a phishing scam where the hackers broke into the human resources system with these compromised logins, changed bank account numbers, and stole a month of pay from these users. The leader at D was very sensitive to this issue and was planning on performing test phishes of the users. Leader G related that a set of “problem users” exist at the institution who were frequently compromised by phishing schemes and H noted that it was usually a faculty member who was compromised by this type of attack. A summary of responses related to the human factor theme is shown in Table 10.

Leaders at all of the institutions realized that students were an enormous source of risk and most had taken steps to eliminate or reduce this risk. The leaders at G and H had totally outsourced the student network and had third-party Internet service providers (ISP) sell services to students independently. The leaders at B, D, and E had segmented

the student network away from the rest of the network as a means to reduce risk to their institutions. The leader at A did not believe in blocking applications on the student

Table 10
Human Factor Impediment Response Summary

Institution	Responses
A	There is no formalized training yet but they are planning for it. During security awareness month they sent out a weekly training email.
B	User acceptance has been a challenge. Security adds a burden on users and makes them less productive. Users are used to getting their way so it has not been easy to impose security measures.
C	Users are involved in unsafe practices and sharing of computer credentials. Faculty are sharing usernames and passwords with student workers.
D	There were a couple users phished and their Google accounts compromised. Because of their universal password, hackers got in and changed account numbers on direct deposit and stole a paycheck.
E	The leader believes human beings will take the easiest route. Their users believe that security is an IT problem.
F	The leader believes that changing people's mindset is difficult. People don't realize the scope of the data they have and its vulnerability.
G	New employees are problem users and are getting phished. If training was in place, it needs to be from the first day on job.
H	Users are too trusting and the suspicious nature that is needed is not there. Users cannot fathom that someone would try to break into systems.

network because of a belief that students would just go around the blocks with proxy servers. However, peer to peer applications that could lead to the downloading of copyrighted material were blocked. Institution C had no rules that isolated students from the rest of the network and no applications were currently blocked. However, there had been discussions at C regarding the best approach to the isolation of the student network. The students at Institution F were on the same network as the classrooms but applications were not blocked. However, the applications were throttled so that bandwidth was equitably distributed throughout campus. There had been numerous complaints that gaming systems did not work on the network at Institution F but the Leader there worked with students as much as possible to fix these issues. Leader F also believed that blocking applications on the student network would result in them finding a way around

the blocks. A summary of responses related to the student factor theme is shown in Table 11.

Table 11
Student Factor Impediment Response Summary

Institution	Responses
A	The students know how to get around blocks with proxies and other methods. They do block peer to peer applications.
B	Student issues have been eliminated by isolating them on their own network. It is as if they are on an outside network.
C	Students do not care about anything security related. Students complain about network setup and limitations. There has been talk of putting students on a separate connection.
D	Students are totally segregated and have open networks. They block peer to peer applications such as file sharing.
E	They throttle bandwidth for peer to peer and other malicious applications. They make it difficult to share and download with throttled bandwidth. It is not prevented but sharply curtailed due to lack of resources.
F	The student network is on the same with classrooms and they are the ISP. They see apps monopolizing bandwidth. Student gaming systems go through the corporate firewall. There have been student complaints.
G	There was a big student push to get better performance on the network and wireless. They could not afford to do it or support it so they outsourced it. SLA on student side forces vendor to keep bandwidth where it needs to be.
H	Students are not on the administrative network. They are outsourced with an ISP who provides cable modems to students. Sometimes students utilize administrative wireless network.

Many of the institutions recognized the usefulness of technologies to help secure the network, but cost was a limiting factor. Institution A had utilized technology tools both on user workstations as well as on their routers and servers. The leaders at B, D, F, and G had focused on securing the perimeter with advanced firewalls, demilitarized zones (DMZ), and other perimeter defenses including intrusion detection systems. The leader at E had implemented a variety of technologies including a firewall but also relied on data loss protection (DLP) software that scanned the network for improperly stored data. The anti-virus solution at this institution also had some DLP capability built into the product. The leader at F had segmented network traffic, implemented a single sign-on with Active Directory that supported the password policy, and had placed more

devices in the DMZ. Institution H had implemented a network access control (NAC) system that restricted access to the network as well as an advanced workstation protection software suite. This institution was also contracting with outside agencies for server and log monitoring services. Additionally, they had an outsourced alert system that monitored the network and servers for unusual activity such as persistent unsuccessful login attempts.

There were many interesting thoughts obtained from the interviews that included insights, strategies, vision, and innovations. I believe that this line of the interview questions generated some of the most useful and thought-provoking data of the study. It is one thing to be aware of the impediments to computing security at an institution, but it is quite another to understand how the leader is dealing with the obstacles from the perspective of the leader. These insights were helpful in not only understanding the current status of the respective security implementations, but also provided ideas on how all leaders that are responsible for IT security can successfully approach information security.

The leader at A had a belief that all users at the institution needed to be a part of the computing security program in order for an institution to be successful. Leader B believed that there must be an advocate at the senior leadership level for a successful security implementation. Leader C believed that it is most important to secure the perimeter. Leader D has shifted to a philosophy of mitigation from prevention because of the belief that all institutions would eventually be compromised. This leader also believed that collaboration with other IT and security professionals was critically important. Leader E was pessimistic and did not believe that it was possible to secure the

campus. This leader believed that the landscape was changing too quickly with too many moving parts for a small, private institution to be successful. Leader F also believed in the futility of securing the institution and noted that the only viable way to secure a computer was to turn it off and put it in a box. The leader at Institution G believed that the model applied to physical security should also be applied to digital security. This leader advocated for table top exercises, mock threats, and a raised awareness of vulnerabilities. Leader G emphasized that because the institution was tuition-driven and did not have a strong financial standing, a single breach could put them out of business. Leader H was the most fearful about susceptibility of their users to phishing attacks.

Many of the insights that the leaders provided focused on a lack of resources and alternative ways to address security. Leader H noted the inability to keep pace with new computing security threats and advocated for the use of outside expert resources for security controls due to the inability to afford a dedicated and qualified security employee. Leaders G and F emphasized the importance of utilizing technology solutions to address security issues because of the lack of human resources. Leader E would like to hire a communications person with a part-time security responsibility to help articulate security awareness to the campus so that IT does not have to be saddled with that responsibility. The leaders at A, D, E, F, and H were all supportive of collaboration to share knowledge, ideas and resources. Leaders B and G believed it was important not to waste precious resources on things that did not need to be protected but to instead focus on the highest priorities. A summary of responses related to participant insights is shown in Table 12.

Table 12
Participant Insights Summary

Institution	Responses
A	The leader believes everyone has to be a part of computing security. The leader wants to have someone on staff that is going to be a real stickler on computing security issues is the key.
B	This leader believes it is difficult for security to be a priority if there is no advocate. The leader thinks that it may take a breach to affect change
C	This leader wants to secure the edge. The leader does not want to waste time on things that do not need to be protected.
D	The institution shifted its philosophy from prevention to mitigation. The leader seeks to know the environment and if a breach has occurred. The leader does not believe they are a big target and not at risk.
E	The leader is pessimistic and thinks everyone is lazy and will not follow up on proper security. The leader does not believe they ever really get their arms around security especially at a small institution. The leader believes they may never fully be under control and should focus on the priorities.
F	This leader thinks that two factor authentication will eventually replace passwords. The leader thinks there is no such thing as a secure computer unless it is powered off because even if they believe they have a secure campus, the hackers can still get into systems.
G	The leader believes that ease of use vs high end security is the balance that needs to be considered. The leader is not confident they can fight off any attack. They are tuition driven and it would only take a couple blips to put them out of business.
H	The leader believes social engineering is the biggest risk. The security landscape is constantly changing. The more they can utilize outside professionals and services, the better they believe they are.

Some of the strategies that had been employed by the institutions reflected the desire to reduce risk. Institutions G and H had completely outsourced their student networks and institutions B, D, E and had isolated students on a separate network. Institutions A and F were blocking or throttling applications on student networks. Institutions A, D, E, and H either had cyber-insurance or were actively obtaining it so that the risk of a breach could be shared with other organizations. Finally, leader H had taken advantage of outside security consultants to ensure that effective solutions were in place.

There had also been strategies communicated in the interviews that I believe could be classified as innovations. Institution A was using an outside standards-based consultant for advice on which products and services were optimal and this consultant

also helped to negotiate pricing and contracts. This organization was also using a state-sponsored consortium as a resource to implement controls and to share ideas and experiences. I believe that the complete outsourcing of the student network on campus was an innovative idea which greatly reduced liability and risk to the institution. Another example of an innovation consisted of Institution B sharing a human resource with another institution. Finally, institution H applied for computing security scanning services from the Department of Homeland Security (DHS) and was successfully accepted as a part of the national critical infrastructure which qualified them for these services. A summary of responses related to participant strategies and innovations is shown in Table 13.

Table 13

Participant Strategy and Innovation Summary

Institution	Responses
A	A standards-based institution was used to obtain the best products for IT & security. They are using a consortium as a resource and are utilizing their programs.
B	They advise not to attempt to implement security with current staffing but to invest in people to do it right.
C	They were audited and have used audit questions to help strengthen their security. They have gone through the application process for cyber-insurance.
D	They bought cyber-insurance through a consortium. They are going to begin phishing users in a nice way but it will not be mandatory.
E	The leader collaborates with area CIOs but would like to make it more regular and take advantage of shared ideas and resources.
F	They are looking at sharing a resource with a sister school. They advise testing before implementing security controls. They replaced firewalls, segmented their network, and isolated traffic.
G	The administrative and academic networks are their main focus because the student network is outsourced. Outsourcing was a way to get wireless in the dorms. There is less risk by outsourcing the student network.
H	They contracted with an outside agency to monitor servers and logs.

Evaluation of Findings

Literature review correlation. The findings that were generated from these interviews correlate well with the review of the literature that was performed in this

study. This literature review elicited four themes which included (1) threats and vulnerabilities to information systems of higher education; (2) the human factor related to threats of security; (3) existing models and strategies of computing security; and (4) impediments to higher educational information computing security. The interview questions were designed using these themes as a guide, and the data from the institutional leaders demonstrated that issues within these themes were salient and relevant. Additionally, the responses to these interview questions emphatically supported the literature.

Threats and vulnerabilities were addressed by institutional leaders during the discussion of computing security impediments. One of the greatest threats noted by the leaders was phishing attempts on their users. The leaders explained that they felt their users were not prepared and were vulnerable to attack, however, the formal user training component of their security implementations seems to have been given the least time and effort. The literature showed that more than 90% of breaches occurred as a result of phishing attacks yet the leaders have failed to apply adequate resources to this vulnerability (Kearney & Kruger, 2014).

Several of the leaders acknowledged the broad threats from around the world and have attempted to block portions of the globe or certain applications such as peer-to-peer software that can cause legal liability to the institution. Many of the institutions recognized that their users were not prepared for the broad array of threats and that students are even more vulnerable. As a result, most of the institutions had either removed the student networks from their networks or had applied stringent access control lists (ACL) to isolate this traffic. However, the two institutions that had not taken

measures to isolate the student networks were currently considering a means to do so. The literature agrees that there are many varied threats to institutions due to the development of applications and technologies that can cause harm to an individual or organization (Hazelwood & Koon-Magnin, 2013).

The institutional leaders had also recognized threats from campus technologies, and some of these technologies were specific to higher education. Though wireless access is not exclusively used by higher education, the leaders have encountered difficulties in securing this technology due to institutional expectations of openness and availability. One of the leaders voiced apprehension about the new push for distance learning because of the associated security risk while another leader articulated concern about cloud technologies and the inability to secure them. All of the leaders felt pressure from risk due to the conflicting priorities of adequately securing campus technologies and political pressure from the campus community that does not want to experience change or inconvenience. Many scholars agree that eLearning systems, as well as other educational technologies, pose a distinct risk to the institution due to the loss of control of geographically diverse systems (Al-Ibrahim, 2012; Arpaci et al., 2015; Asllani, 2012; Bambauer, 2014; Ben Arfa Rabai et al., 2012; Budhrani & Sridaran, 2015; Dennen, 2015; Harris & Pattern; 2014, Jalal-Karim, 2013; Shonola & Joy, 2015).

Several leaders described the risk that resulted from the proliferation of technologies and devices that were adopted before they could be fully vetted and secured. Various consumer-grade technologies were reported to be in use, and one of the leaders noted that consumer-grade products typically do not have a high level of security. Other leaders acknowledged the inability to test all of the technologies that were being rapidly

deployed by users with no thought to risk to the institution. These assertions correlated with the literature which indicated that technologies are commonly adopted in higher education without comprehension of the security risks involved (Zamzuri et al., 2013).

The human factor theme from the review of the literature was acknowledged as one of the most pervasive problems faced by the institutions due to political pressure not to adopt security controls, susceptibility to phishing attacks, inability to comprehend the risks involved, and the naïve nature of users which caused them to be too trusting of the environment in which they operated. The intertwined nature of humans with information systems underscores the weak link as described in the literature due to the insider threat, phishing threat, and training and awareness issues (Abdul Majid et al., 2105; Crossler et al., 2013; Hu et al., 2012; Kearny & Kruger, 2014; Lebek et al., 2014; Pfleeger & Caputo, 2012; Solic et al., 2012).

The leader from institution E described the mindset of their users which demonstrated the belief that computing security was an IT problem. Almost all of the leaders cited a lack of human resources and funds as the rationale for not being able to effectively implement training and awareness programs. The leader from E also related the insight that the awareness and training program may be better handled by someone who was skilled in human communication such as someone from the Public Relations department rather than IT. Most of the data from the interviews about the human factor of computing security focused on the insufficient level of wariness of the users regarding phishing attacks. All of the leaders realized that technological systems are not as vulnerable as the human and that focused attention needs to be applied to this risk.

There were many computing security strategies in place at the institutions, but none of the leaders felt that their efforts and solutions were sufficient. Only a few of the institutions employed formal computing security control frameworks and most seemed to focus attention toward security controls only when time and money could be spared. Several of the leaders were proactive in seeking outside resources and collaboration, and these leaders seemed to be more knowledgeable and had stronger security implementations in place. My overall impression, however, is that computing security strategies at these institutions are serendipitous and disorganized with each leader advocating a different direction. This lack of organization, vision, comprehension, and priority agrees with the literature that highlights these issues (Bougaardt & Kyobe, 2011; Sangani et al., 2012).

The theme from the literature that focused on educational impediments strongly correlated with the interviews of the institutional leaders. The leaders all voiced incidents where the academic principles of openness, freedom, and tradition collided with security initiatives. These incidents included password policy resistance, disputes related to management of servers, resistance to the removal of rights from computers, non-compliance with policies, resistance to blocking portions of the globe, and inactivity lockout timers. All of the leaders indicated that future computing security initiatives would undoubtedly lead to more conflict and they shared their reluctance to antagonize faculty with additional restrictions.

In addition to the academic impediments of tradition, freedom, and openness, the leaders corroborated the other themes present in the literature which included student-centered vulnerabilities, lack of resources, lack of awareness, decentralized culture and

systems, absence of policies, enforcement of policies, and lack of senior management support (Kam & Katteral, 2014). The leaders gave overwhelming support to the notion of a shortage of resources for security initiatives. The leaders also voiced support for the high risk associated with student impediments, but most had dealt with these issues by isolating access to their systems. The absence of a formal computing security program seemed to stem from a lack of focus on computing security by the leaders. Finally, lack of senior management support was evident at most of the institutions and had contributed to perfunctory computing security implementations.

Research questions. The evaluation of the findings related to the research questions of the study will briefly be addressed in this section and will be more thoroughly discussed in the final chapter of this work. The research questions were focused on the discernment of operational impediments present at the institutions that led to less than optimal implementation of computing security controls. An explanation for which provisions were lacking in the maintenance of controls was sought as well as the understanding of which resources were necessary to address the operational barriers that would lead to efficacious implementations of computing security.

The operational barrier that was overwhelmingly voiced as the predominant impediment consisted of the lack of human and budgetary resources. All of the leaders described the dire need for additional funds to improve their computing security initiatives, and almost all of them were unable to justify additional funds with senior leaders. Many of the leaders were resigned to the fact that no additional funds would be made available for this purpose and a strategy of making due with existing IT resources had been employed. While two of the institutions were able to make a case for some

additional funding, others felt that a breach would be necessary in order for senior leaders to understand the risks and need for additional funding.

The other operational barrier that was expressed with unanimity was the human factor and the pervasive risks associated with phishing attacks. However, only one of the leaders had implemented a formalized training and awareness program. Barriers that reflected impediments specific to educational institutions were expressed that included academic philosophies, traditions, freedom, and openness. I discovered during the interviews that IT leaders were reluctant to confront or antagonize academic campus constituents with the burden of additional security controls. Comprehension and leadership issues were also voiced by the leaders which constrained their ability to effectively implement computing security controls. Student impediments did not seem to be a pressing concern to leaders due to their prevailing strategies that attempted to work around student vulnerabilities by placing them on a separate network.

The second research question was addressed by participants who provided insights on why existing provisions were not adequate and this theme was also explained in the literature. The primary rationale for the inadequacy of existing resources and strategies, according to the literature, stems from a lack of institutional support as well as a lack of understanding (Holter & Seganish, 2014; Sangani et al., 2012). The lack of resources theme was repeatedly underscored in this narrative and appears to be a product of the academic model that is in place at most institutions. Because educational costs are quickly rising, funding sources are decreasing, and public sentiment has taken issue with the rate of increase, it is critical that these institutions look for efficiencies and ways to reduce costs (Hodgman, 2014). Therefore, those aspects of the operation that are not

deemed a high priority are susceptible to cuts and computing security seems to fit into this category because of its perceived low return on investment. This approach to funding computing security seems to be a result of lack of understanding by both senior leadership and most of the interviewed IT leaders as well. One of the leaders expressed fear that a single breach could potentially put the institution out of business due to its weak financial position. This acknowledgment of risk did not seem to have a corresponding investment by the institutions.

The final research question focused on understanding which resources would be necessary for effective security implementations and the interviewed leaders have all related their vision on this question. All expressed the need for additional human and financial resources but one leader explained with surety that it would take two dedicated people with an additional \$500,000 budget. Other leaders expressed hope for at least one additional resource and a moderate increase in budget. However, all of the leaders believed that the greatest need was a dedicated resource who could give the institution a focus on security and be an advocate for change. One of the leaders noted the desire to have someone on staff that would be ten times more scared about computing security than this leader was at the moment. This notion underscores the need at these institutions for a leader or champion with a tight focus on computing security who can follow industry best practices, adopt a formal computing security framework, articulate needs, lead organizational change, and justify adequate funding.

Rival explanations. Rival explanations to deficiencies in computing security need to be considered to balance the discussion on effective computing security and to verify the findings of the study (Yin, 2014). This means that other factors should be

identified and considered that could cause ineffective security implementations rather than those listed in the literature and research questions. These rival explanations may include (1) available computing strategies do not support academic institution unique aspects of freedom and openness; (2) an evolved vision that suggests that computing security is a low priority; (3) a shortage of resources available to support the high costs of security controls; (4) inadequate security measures available to secure educational technologies; or (5) available computing security strategies do not support student entertainment expectations as shown in Table 14.

Table 14
Rival Explanations for Lack of Computing Security

Number	Rival Explanation
1	The available computing strategies do not support the unique aspects of academic institutions that include freedom and openness.
2	There exists an evolved vision by leadership that suggests that computing security is a low priority.
3	There is a shortage of resources available to support the high costs of security controls.
4	There are inadequate security measures available to secure educational technologies.
5	The available computing security strategies do not support student entertainment expectations.

The notion that computing security controls run contrary to academic freedom and openness and, therefore, should not be implemented suggests that appropriate teaching and research cannot occur in a secure environment. It is obvious that the lack of an adoption of computing security controls by academic constituents does not override the high risks associated with a failure to implement computing security. The study participants indicated that the issue was more about the reluctance to change than compromising the academic model. This fact is supported by the fact that one of the participating institutions was able to successfully remove control of the academic servers from faculty and transfer control to IT. This institution was still able to continue

operation after this transfer of responsibility occurred. Other leaders cited compromise in getting faculty to change their passwords on a periodic basis. The changing of passwords in a systematic manner to a strong password did not seem to compromise the academic functions at this institution. In addition, the acceptance of inactivity timeouts by faculty had also not prevented faculty from accomplishing their mission. Therefore, the rival explanation that security controls did not fit within the academic context does not appear to be valid but, rather, it seems that faculty at these institutions were intent on the status quo at the expense of institutional security.

Another possible rival explanation to effective computing security at academic institutions involves the supposition that educational technologies cannot be secured due to their unique aspects. The literature disagrees with this concern and prescribes specific remedies for securing distance learning, e-commerce, and other web technologies employed by academic institutions. Remedies include penetration tests, web monitoring software, internal and external security audits, automated security tools, and email monitoring tools (Vakharia et al., 2013). Additionally, other remedies include elimination of broken links on websites, installation of the latest patches to combat cross-site scripting, secure web form design, secure configuration of web server, masking of email addresses, disallowing uploads to a website, fixing of configuration errors, elimination of auto-complete for passwords, and masking of web server characteristics (Al-Ibrahim & Al-Deen, 2014).

Perhaps one of the most compelling rival explanations for inadequate computing security at institutions of higher education is that there simply is not enough money to implement all of the relevant controls. This concern was addressed by two of the leaders

where one stated that it would take a breach to enable dollars to be freed up for security purposes and the other experienced a breach scare which resulted in the allocation of dollars toward security. This fact implies that computing security had not been made a priority, had not been communicated effectively to senior leadership, and had not been sufficiently understood by them. If organizational leadership truly comprehended the risks and consequences associated with a breach then a moderate amount of resources could be made available which is supported by Leader G's assertion that a breach could put the institution out of business. One leader stated that periodically there were dollars available for spending, but these resources tended to be invested in something "bright and shiny". The leaders also indicated that they had used creative ways in the past to obtain security funding such as fee increases, room adjustments, or outsourcing of services. These practices prove that it is possible to obtain funds for important priorities at these institutions when needs arise.

The rival explanation that computing security controls do not support the student residential experience on campus seems to also have been refuted by the interview data in this study. Though most of the participants recognized the seriousness of the risk imposed by student entertainment technologies and acknowledged the importance of student satisfaction within the residential experience, they were not willing to jeopardize the security of the institution toward these realizations. The majority of the participants had either opted to completely remove the student network from the campus network or strictly enforce ACLs that prevented access to academic and administrative networks which imposed isolation on them. This tactic allowed the IT leaders to provide almost

unfettered access of entertainment resources to students without the associated risks to the campus network.

Finally, the rival explanation that computing security is a low priority at educational institutions and not worthy of time and resources also seems to have been refuted by the interview data and the literature. While it was true that some of the institutions interviewed did not recognize computing security as a priority, others did. The leader at institution C clearly did not see computing security as a priority but this may have been due to a lack of understanding and vision as mentioned in the literature (Kam & Katteral, 2014). Leader G, however, clearly understood the risks and priority as evidenced by the insight that one breach could put the institution out of business.

Theoretical foundation. The theoretical foundation on which this study was based involves two theories that include the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Organizational Learning Theory (OLT). The TPB was applied to the human factor theme that discussed user vulnerability and attempts to understand user attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (PBC) as well as antecedent beliefs. The review of the literature and the data collected from the interviews seem to support the use of this theory because it was a predominant topic during the interviews as well as prominently present in the literature. The interview participants were very vocal in describing user perceptions of computing security and offered explanations that fit within the theoretical framework. Some of the participants reminisced about user reactions to training programs, awareness campaigns, and efforts to gain user support. One leader noted that users would not buy into security initiatives unless they understood the value of the training and unless it was presented to them in a way that convinced them it was in their

best interests in terms of rewards and punishments. The literature supports this assertion and emphasizes understandable training that identifies both rewards and punishments (Hu et al., 2012). This notion suggests that IT leaders responsible for computing security should consider the tenets of the TPB in order to implement effective training and awareness programs.

Single loop OLT is understood as a cyclical process that recognizes institutional errors, corrects them, and then looks for additional errors (Huang & Shih, 2011). This fits the other three themes of the literature review which include information security threats and vulnerabilities in higher education information systems, information security strategies, and obstacles to information security. The study participants addressed the dynamics and struggles related to a recognition of errors stemming from limited budgets, limited resources, limited skillsets, academic freedom, residential computing expectations, wireless availability, and distance learning infrastructure. The leaders expressed the desire to correct these errors with a variety of efforts. The lack of resources issue was addressed by making a case to senior leaders as well as utilizing IT funds for security initiatives. Academic impediments were met with caution by participants with a “give and take” posture as well as a gradual evolution of computing security initiatives. One leader noted that security breaches in the press had raised awareness and had somewhat reduced dissension on campus associated with the implementation of security controls. Distance learning and other technologies had been better secured by some of the participants than others. While some were pessimistic about the ability to vet all of the new technologies that arrived on campus, others were investing in technology solutions, collaborating with others, and taking advantage of

consortium resources as an aid in bolstering security. Finally, the student network had mostly been isolated or outsourced in an attempt to correct the error of letting it intermingle with traffic on academic and administrative networks. OLT should, therefore, be carefully considered as a viable model to analyze and correct institutional computing security flaws.

Interpretation of findings. The interpretation and meaning of these findings seem to be straight forward and in line with the study purpose and problem as shown in Table 15. The findings indicate that there were significant operational barriers to computing security at institutions of higher education. Simply put, the implementation of computing security controls in any organization is difficult and requires a comprehensive vision, organized approach, and adequate resources (Bougaardt & Kyobe, 2011; Sangani et al., 2012). Implementation of computing security at small and private institutions of higher education is even more difficult because of the existence of unique philosophical and operational barriers (Kam & Katteral, 2014). The findings of this study indicate that small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. are subject to all of the operational barriers described in the literature and, in addition, the findings show that the current provisions that are lacking include institutional support and comprehension.

The lack of institutional support and comprehension is evident by the inadequate amount of resources allocated to computing security at the institutions as well as the lack of understanding, support, and investment by both senior leadership and IT leadership. The data suggests that a thorough understanding of computing security risks and strategies is necessary as a first step for both IT leadership and senior leadership. The disorganized and piecemeal approach to computing security by the interviewed

institutions was overwhelmingly apparent by the lack of the adoption of an organized computing security framework such as NIST, Sans, ISO27001, Common Criteria, Coras, Octave, TMT or CySeMol (Gillies, 2011; Mbowe et al., 2014). A security framework should serve as both a guide and a thermometer that is able to provide a roadmap and feedback to an institution about the effectiveness of their computing security controls. It is obvious that if there is no organized and systematic plan, there can be only limited success to efficacious computing security. A systematic model or framework is highlighted as a necessity in the literature and is absent in practice at these institutions.

Table 15
Findings of the Study

Number	Finding
1	There are significant operational barriers and impediments to computing security at institutions of higher education as described in the literature review.
2	A primary provision that is lacking for effective computing security includes institutional financial support to fund security initiatives.
3	A primary provision that is lacking for effective computing security includes institutional comprehension of computing security vulnerabilities and necessary solutions.
4	A systematic model or framework is absent in practice at these institutions which should serve as both a guide and a thermometer to provide a roadmap and feedback to an institution.
5	The practical utility of this study consists of bringing to light the inadequacies of computing security at small and private institutions of higher education in the United States and providing a foundation for a conversation to affect change.

These results were anticipated and they were emphatically confirmed during the participant interviews. I can fully appreciate the negative impact of the articulated operational barriers on computing security implementations as well as the inherent difficulty of implementing sound computing security controls. The overall complexity and enormous scope of organizational computing security requires an organized and systematic approach to computing security implementation as well as firm institutional support. This was evidenced by one of the leaders who stated that they did not know

what they did not know. These critical components seem to be absent in small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. and, with the addition of the philosophical and operational barriers described in this study, a monumental challenge exists for personnel responsible for computing security at these institutions.

Finally, the practical utility of this study consists of bringing to light the inadequacies of computing security at small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. and providing a foundation for a conversation to affect change. Not only were there significant operational barriers present in these institutions, but there was an overwhelming lack of institutional support and comprehension. This means that these institutions are vulnerable to nefarious individuals and the current strategy of minimal attention to computing security may cause more of these institutions to be compromised which could lead to organizational failure. Moreover, organizational leadership must recognize the importance of reducing risk and protecting their assets with a balanced and appropriate response that will reduce operational barriers, provide adequate resources, and create a culture of computing security at their institutions that involves every person in the campus community.

Summary

This chapter provided an overview of the interview process, an individual summary of the eight institutions that were interviewed, a detailed analysis of the cases, and an evaluation of the findings. The interview questions were designed to discover operational barriers as well as institutional successes, failures, insights, innovations, and vision. The unanimous concern of the interviewed IT leaders focused on the lack of time and resources for computing security, and that stopgap measures were currently in place

that utilized IT budgets and human resources to make up for the lack of dedicated security resources. The IT leaders chronicled battles with faculty, existence of political issues, the proliferation of untested technology, lack of senior leadership support, the human factor, and student issues as operational impediments to computing security. Many insights were obtained that included the need for a campus culture of security, reduction of risk, a philosophy of mitigation, and the need for planning and preparation as well as the pervasive fear about the phishing of their users.

Rival explanations were discussed in order to balance the discussion on effective computing security and to strengthen the findings of this study. The theoretical foundation on which this study was based was explained that involved two theories including the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Organizational Learning Theory (OLT). Both of these theories were linked to the results of the study and provided the rationale for the development of user awareness and training programs as well as the correction of institutional problems related to computing security.

Finally, the interpretation and meaning of the study were presented that demonstrated that these institutions were subject to the operational barriers described in the literature that were specific to both higher education and small to medium enterprises. The findings show that, in addition to the operational barriers, there was little organization, vision, or institutional support of the computing security program at these institutions. Organizational leadership must recognize the importance of reducing risk and protecting their assets and balance an appropriate response that will reduce operational barriers, provide adequate resources, and create a culture of computing security at their institutions that involves every person in the campus community. The

practical utility of this study consists of bringing to light the inadequacies of computing security at small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. and providing a foundation for discussion to alter the present state of computing security at these institutions. These conclusions are carefully described in chapter five of this study which provides the conclusions, recommendations, and implications of the study.

Chapter 5: Implications, Recommendations, and Conclusions

Small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. have expectations of reliable, ubiquitous, expedient, and secure computing resources like all businesses. However, only limited resources are available at these small institutions to meet those expectations which requires technology leaders to balance available resources with stakeholder demands and computing security best practices. This constraint means that technology leaders at these institutions must carefully weigh the priority of security initiatives against limited human and budgetary resources to provide a sound security strategy. Because institutions of higher education have unique operational philosophies and traditions that strive for collaboration and openness, it is extremely challenging to implement security initiatives because they often collide with these principles.

The purpose of this study was to examine eight small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. and to more thoroughly understand the impact that their operational philosophies and impediments have on computing security. Data was gathered from these eight randomly selected institutions using semi-structured telephone interviews that sought to discover contributing factors, status, insights, perspectives, strategies, and innovations related to computing security implementations. The interview questions were designed using a foundational review of the literature in conjunction with research questions that desired to understand unique operational computing security impediments, the rationale for computing security shortcomings, and insights on necessary resources to implement effective computing security on campus.

A qualitative multi-case study design was utilized to examine computing security at small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. A descriptive case format

was utilized to better focus on the understanding of a phenomenon rather than a single individual or an institution (Yin, 2014). Case study research is ideal for answering how and why questions and involves the employment of observational techniques to study a phenomenon in its original habitat (Stake, 2006). A multi-case study format is stronger than a single case study because it allows more compelling evidence to be assembled than would be possible with just a single case (Yin, 2014). A replicative approach was used that drew on eight institutions randomly selected from the entire population of these small and private colleges and universities.

The design steps utilized a logical framework to connect data to the research questions that consisted of (1) research questions; (2) propositions; (3) units of analysis; (4) rationale to connect data to research questions; and (5) logic to interpret findings. Three research questions were created that sought to understand unique operational impediments to computing security, computing security shortcomings, and insights regarding what would be necessary for effective computing security. The data garnered from the interviews of technology leaders at these institutions was used in a comparative analysis, synthesis, refutation of rival explanations, linkage to a theoretical foundation, and a correlation with the literature. This allowed me to draw conclusions and make recommendations based on the interviews and the literature.

The primary limitation of this study consisted of the sensitivity of the topic related to the interview questions which could result in a reluctance of the leaders to divulge the true state of their computing security environment. It was thought that technology leaders may not have been willing to disclose information about their security posture that placed themselves or their institution in an unfavorable light. However, a

requirement of the Northcentral University Internal Review Board mandated that the technology leaders must be solicited as private individuals rather than institutional representatives and their responses must be construed as personal opinion. This mandate seemed to put the study participants at ease and allowed for more open and candid responses. In addition, the researcher believed that assurances that the interview conversation would not be recorded along with promised confidentiality and anonymity would further give participants the confidence to provide open and honest answers.

Ethical considerations were applied at each stage of the study in compliance with Northcentral University Internal Review Board (IRB) requirements to increase reliability and credibility of the study. The study was carefully reviewed by the IRB and no solicitation of participants or data collection occurred until their approval was granted. Solicitation and informed consent documents were created and disseminated to prospective participants to assure them that the study was an ethical project and that considerations of risk, rights, and benefits were clearly articulated. The consent document explained the measures that were taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity as well as the methods employed to properly de-identify and care for the data. All study participants were required to read, understand, sign, and return the informed consent document before an interview occurred.

This chapter will present the implications of the study and will primarily address the findings and results from the data relative to the three research questions as shown in Table 16. In addition, the results will be placed in context that ties them back to the original study problem and purpose. The significance of the results will be examined and arguments will be presented that suggest a contribution to the literature. A linkage to the

applied nature of the study and computing security profession will be given along with the practical nature, “real world” applicability, and utility of this work. Finally, a set of recommendations is presented that provide practical application to the computing security profession along with thoughts for future research. A conclusion is then presented that summarizes the important concepts discussed in this chapter.

Table 16
Implications

Number	Implication
1	There are real and pervasive threats to computing resources present at small and private institutions of higher education.
2	The responses from the IT leaders indicate the inability to mount a coordinated and comparable response to the acknowledged threats.
3	The IT leaders have been unsuccessful in not only articulating and justifying resources for computing security purposes, but were unable to comprehend the importance of the risks and mount a coordinated approach.
4	The failure of computing security implementations at these institutions stems from a lack of comprehension, leadership, and institutional support.
5	A holistic understanding of computing security is critical in order to identify resources, articulate needs, educate leadership, educate users, and successfully implement controls.

Implications

Research question one. The first research question asked which operational barriers impeded these small and private institutions of higher education from implementing computing security controls. The most overwhelmingly voiced impediment by the IT leaders consisted of the lack of dedicated budgetary resources available for computing security. The leaders were unanimous with their responses in that there was not sufficient funding for computing security initiatives and that it was necessary to utilize funds from the IT operational budgets for this purpose. The leaders explained that the lack of resources for computing security projects caused them to be prioritized alongside IT projects which seemed to dilute their priority.

Leader A complained about the shortage of time allocated to computing security because of competition with other IT projects. Leader B cited time and money as the biggest obstacles to computing security because of the lack of a dedicated budget. Leader C voiced the concern that there was not sufficient budget for IT projects much less computing security projects which connoted a lower priority for computing security. Leaders A and D expressed that they did have adequate IT budgets and had used excess IT funds to direct toward computing security projects. Leader E was in agreement that there were insufficient funds for computing security and leader F articulated the dire need not only for additional computing security funds, but additional IT funds as well. Leader G was not optimistic about securing additional funding and thought that it would take a computing security breach to make additional funds available.

The lack of funding for computing security at these institutions implies that computing security is a lower priority for both senior leadership and IT leadership. Leaders A and D noted that they could get funding for projects if they made a good case for them because their leadership understood the need for effective computing security. This suggests that funding could be made available for important projects at these institutions when IT leaders were able to articulate and justify a need and when senior leadership fully understood the need for the project. This notion underscores the importance of the comprehension of computing security priorities by both IT leadership and senior leadership. Because budgetary resources were extremely constrained at these institutions as voiced by their IT leaders, it was necessary to prioritize and strategically allocate resources for computing security projects.

The lack of a dedicated human resource was also voiced as a unanimous impediment by the IT leaders with respect to the first research question. Institution B explained that there was not enough time for IT projects much less computing security projects. All of the institutions expressed the inability to justify and fund an additional human resource for computing security but institutions A & B were recently able to get a half-time resource in place. However, the leaders at these institutions admitted that the IT operation seemed to take precedence over security projects for these partially dedicated resources. Leaders E & G believed the only way for them to obtain computing skillsets was to invest in their IT personnel but they acknowledged that it took time to educate staff and that there was the risk that staff could leave the institution during or after this investment.

The implications related to the human resource impediment suggests that there is no focus on computing security as related by leader C. Leader G noted the importance of having a dedicated resource to create a focus on the problem but lamented that they did not even have someone dedicated to networking. This assertion also implies a lower priority on computing security instead of a balanced approach which is necessary when there is not adequate funding. Leader A highlighted the critical nature of computing security and the need for a dedicated resource in order to create a focused effort at these institutions by acknowledging the need for someone on campus who was ten times more scared about computing security than this leader. This statement also has an implication of lower priority for computing security by admitting that the leader was not as concerned about computing security as is optimal.

The philosophical impediments of academic freedom, openness, and traditions were evident at these institutions and most of the leaders have experienced conflict with academic personnel over computing security initiatives. Leader A noted that the IT department was accused of spying on the faculty when an IT vulnerability scanning tool was discovered. Leader F related the battles with their faculty senate over computing security controls and leader H described a posture of compromise to get faculty to adhere to a password change policy. Violations of policy were frequent and open as related by Leader C and faculty had no problem with using new technologies which may put the institution at risk as noted by leader E. All of the leaders believed that future computing security initiatives could cause more conflict with faculty and I sensed a reluctance of leaders to antagonize leaders with additional security controls.

The academic impediment implications suggest that computing security initiatives have already collided with academic principles and that no clear path to computing security exists in this context. The reluctance to implement additional controls for fear of further antagonizing faculty implies weak leadership at the IT leadership level and lack of support from senior leadership. The lack of support at the senior leadership level may also stem from fear of antagonizing faculty but certainly stems from lack of comprehension of the importance of computing security controls as evidenced by responses from leaders B, C, and G. The implication that a politically powerful faculty contingent can prevent sound business practices from occurring suggests an educational model that may need to be altered to allow computing security initiatives to be successfully implemented.

The human factor impediments with respect to the first research question imply that humans are, in fact, the weakest link to computing security as suggested in the literature and responses from the IT leaders support this assertion (Kearney & Kruger, 2014). However, there was not a corresponding effort to address the acknowledgment of high risk by the IT leaders. The literature suggests that there is an untapped potential in enlisting the help of a trained user contingent (Posey et al., 2013). Only institution E had implemented a mandatory training and awareness program but HR often forgot to remind users to complete the program. This implies not only a mediocre effort at institution E, but a failed opportunity at all of the institutions to strengthen the weakest link and enlist the users as an asset to a security program rather than to accept them as a liability to it.

The leadership and comprehension impediment with respect to the first research question also have implications for poor computing security implementations. The leadership deficiencies were present at both the IT leadership level and the senior leadership level as evidenced by the interview data. The IT leaders at most of the institutions voiced concerns about the lack of support from senior leadership and Leader G expressed a profound lack of support and priority from senior leadership. Leader B related that senior leadership did not want anything implemented that would cause complaints. These statements imply that senior leadership had not been adequately educated which may also imply that IT leaders had done a poor job in providing education to them. A lack of comprehension was evident from both senior leaders and IT leaders and both of these groups represented impediments to computing security at these institutions.

There were also technology-based impediments at these institutions that are applicable to the first research question. Some of the leaders regretted that educational technologies had been adopted without testing them for security. All of the leaders agreed that their wireless implementations were not secure and problematic. Leader E admitted that there was no way to properly test all of the technologies on campus and Leader G explained that many consumer-based technologies were in use that put the institution at risk. This implies a weak computing security posture because technologies were able to be added to the network without proper testing and vetting. The fact that the leaders acknowledged this problem and were fully aware of it suggests an uncoordinated security effort and possibly a failure in leadership.

The student factor impediment was not a large factor at these institutions although institutions E and F still were contending with blocking and throttling applications on the student network. All of the other institutions had either outsourced the student network or logically separated by access control lists. This implies a realization of the high risk associated with student network use and the ability of most of the leaders to effectively mitigate this risk. This also implies that the IT leaders could apply the principles and resolve used to reduce risk from the student network to other areas of the institution.

The overall implications of the operational impediment theme in the first research question suggest that there are real and pervasive threats present with respect to computing resources at these institutions. The responses from the leaders indicate the inability to mount a coordinated and comparable response to the acknowledged threats except in the case of the isolation of the student network. Most of the IT leaders were unsuccessful in not only articulating and justifying resources for computing security

purposes, but were unable to comprehend the importance of the risks and mount a coordinated campaign. This was evidenced by Leader D who did not think their institution was a target and Leader H who stated that they did not know what they did not know and Leader E who did not know where to begin. The ability of most of the IT leaders to effectively deal with the student network impediment suggests that security controls can be put into place when a threat is properly identified and understood.

Research question two. The second research question asks why current provisions are lacking in the ability to maintain information security controls. The literature suggests that the failure of computing security implementation stems from a lack of comprehension and lack of institutional support that leads to the dedication of insufficient resources (Holter & Seganish, 2014; Sangani et al., 2012). The responses from the IT leaders supports the assertions from the literature because many responses were given that indicate lack of comprehension and support as described in the previous section related to operational impediments. The operational impediments that seem to directly affect this theme include comprehension and leadership. A domino effect seems to be in play where lack of comprehension by IT leadership leads to lack of comprehension by senior leadership. Lack of comprehension by senior leadership leads to insufficient allocation of resources for computing security purposes. This implies that education of IT leaders should be the first step in dealing with current insufficient provisions related to computing security controls.

However, comprehension is not the only impediment that has an impact on the second research question. There is also the question of leadership and its effectiveness that directly impacts the security implementation. As was discussed previously, the

leaders at institutions D, E, F, and H seemed to be very knowledgeable about computing security. This implies that comprehension alone is not sufficient for effective computing security. An element of strong leadership on both the IT leadership level and the senior leadership level is also necessary. Also, politically powerful user contingents exist on campus that are able to thwart the implementation of security controls. Strong leadership and support are necessary at all levels to bring user contingents into the fold and cooperate with computing security initiatives. This means that both comprehension and leadership are necessary to successfully implement security controls.

Research question three. The final research question sought to understand what resources would be necessary to implement effective computing security at these institutions. The leaders all expressed the need for additional budgetary and human resource support. While only leader B gave a precise estimate of two additional resources and \$500,000 in additional funds for the budget, the other leaders did not know exactly what would be necessary. This fact implies a lack of comprehension and understanding of what is necessary for effective computing security. This lack of comprehension suggests that IT leaders must first educate themselves on computing security concepts so that they can mount a coordinated effort. It is impossible to effectively implement computing security if the leaders do not comprehend all of the many varied risks, strategies, and approaches. Therefore, a holistic understanding of computing security is critical in order to identify resources, articulate needs, educate leadership, educate users, and successfully implement controls.

Relation to study problem and purpose. The findings and implications of this study directly correspond to the research problem and purpose. The research problem

focused on the tension between user expectations and effective computing security at small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. The research problem acknowledged the limited resources, skillsets, and understanding present at these institutions as suggested by the review of the literature. The problem statement also highlighted the difficulty that IT leaders face in balancing user expectations with sound computing security practices. The participating IT leaders vehemently acknowledged the pressures felt by stakeholder expectations. The findings as supported by the participant responses explicitly corroborated the presence of limited resources and skillsets and implicitly corroborated the lack of understanding of both IT leaders and senior leaders. The leaders admitted that the proper priority for computing security resources had not yet been found and that adequate computing security solutions are not yet in place.

The study purpose sought to examine eight small and private institutions of higher education to discover which operational barriers had an impact on computing security implementations. The findings as supported by the eight participant responses overwhelmingly confirmed the presence of the unique operational barriers that negatively impacted their computing security implementations and these barriers have been partially addressed by the leaders but only in a serendipitous manner. Only the student factor operational barrier had been addressed in an effective manner by all but two of the institutions.

Significance. The findings related to the significance of the study highlighted the growing threats to all organizations but particularly underscored the importance of addressing these threats at small and private institutions of higher education due to their unique operational impediments as well as their lack of resources and institutional

support. This finding recommends that leaders at these institutions create a balanced approach to computing security that takes into account both user requirements and security best practices. The responses by the study participants corroborated the need for a careful balance of user expectations with computing security best practices and especially underscored the need for priorities to be established to allow for the most effective application of resources to this problem. Though there was a significant lack of understanding of the overall computing security landscape by study participants by their own admission, the IT leaders were able to demonstrate useful insights, strategies, and innovations based on the knowledge that they currently possess. The objective of the study was to provide a foundation for conversations based on IT leader perspectives and this study certainly accomplished that goal because of the many varied perspectives and insights shared by them.

Contribution to the literature. This study represents a significant contribution to the literature because it fills a gap that had not been previously addressed. The literature currently provides only piecemeal works related to computing security at institutions of higher education and there is no recent work that addresses all of the unique operational impediments in aggregate. In addition, the question of what provisions are lacking for effective computing security and what provisions are necessary for effective computing security at small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. from a holistic perspective is not present. This work contains verbose descriptions about the operational barriers faced by IT leaders responsible for computing security at these institutions as well as perspectives and insights from those who are faced with the dilemma to balance stakeholder needs with computing security best practices

with only limited resources. Though these leaders had not been successful at finding this balance, their experiences and insights provide a foundation for understanding and evaluating strategies that may be successfully employed.

Application and utility to IT security profession. The practical utility of this study lies in bringing to light the current struggles and inadequacies of the computing security environment at small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. It provides a concrete course of action that consists of the adoption of a computing security framework and continuing education of users, IT staff, IT leadership, and senior leadership. The ongoing education of the institution should enable the creation of a campus-wide culture of computing security that transforms users from a computing security liability to a computing security asset.

This work highlights the presence of unique operational barriers that prevent these institutions from implementing effective computing security. Rival explanations were refuted that suggested that computing security solutions were not available to address the unique operational aspects of these institutions. Rather, significant resistance was reported from the interviewed leaders about their users and faculty users in particular. The findings suggest that a thorough understanding of computing security risks and strategies are necessary as the first step for both IT leadership and senior leadership. Additionally, strong leadership is necessary at the IT leadership level coupled with strong support from senior leadership to implement computing security controls. A thorough comprehension of the importance of computing security should enable IT leadership to establish priorities and implement a balanced strategy that can be articulated to senior leadership.

A critical beginning for these institutions is the adoption of a computing security framework such as NIST, Sans, ISO27001, Common Criteria, Coras, Octave, TMT, or CySeMol (Gillies, 2011; Mbowe et al., 2014). These frameworks should serve as both a guide and a means of feedback about the efficacy of computing security at these institutions. The findings emphatically underscore the need for an organized approach due to the complexity, scope, and operational barriers in play. The adoption of a framework will provide a holistic and organized vision and approach to computing security and enable institutions to systematically prioritize, justify, and implement effective computing security controls.

Recommendations

Recommendations for addressing computing security at small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. were developed based on the review of the literature and the data obtained from interviews of personnel responsible for computing security. The recommendations are in priority order and offer an approach that takes into account the operational impediments and limited resources of the institution as shown in Table 17. The advice provided in this section is supported by both the literature and the data from the interviews.

Recommendation one. Educational programs should be the first step toward an approach for computing security because it is difficult to imagine putting effective solutions in place or justifying funding unless a firm comprehension of the security environment is in place. The literature emphasized this point by arguing that one of the main reasons that educational institutions are vulnerable is due to lack of understanding (Bougaardt & Kyobe, 2011; Sangani et al., 2012). The interview responses confirmed

this assertion with the statement from Leader D who did not think their institution was a target, by Leader H who stated that they did not know what they did not know, and Leader E who did not know where to begin.

Table 17
Recommendations

Number	Recommendation
1	Educational programs for all levels of leadership should be the first step toward an approach for computing security.
2	The adoption of a computing security framework as an organized approach should be a priority for the IT leaders.
3	Responsibility for the computing security function should be assigned to someone on campus.
4	A prioritized information security plan should be created.
5	An aggressive and comprehensive user awareness and training program for computing security should be created.
6	An environment of collaboration should be developed.
7	A culture of computing security should be created on campus that involves every person in the organization.

Recommendation two. The adoption of a computing security framework as an organized approach should be a priority for the IT leaders because of the complexity, scope, and operational barriers in play with computing security. There are many frameworks to choose from that include NIST, Sans, ISO27001, Common Criteria, Coras, Octave, TMT and CySeMol and some have been customized to more adequately represent the interests of SMEs (Gillies, 2011; Mbowe et al., 2014). A computing framework will provide a holistic approach and draw on knowledge from experts from around the globe. This framework should serve to offer direction and priority as well as to provide a means of feedback toward computing security efficacy.

Recommendation three. Responsibility for the computing security function should be assigned to an employee on campus. The IT leaders lamented the lack of a dedicated resource to computing security and realized that such a resource could give the institution a sharp focus as stated by leaders A and F. However, the responsibility does

not have to be exclusive nor does it necessarily have to reside in the IT department. The literature suggests that the audit function can aid in providing a focus and accountability to the actual security function (Rahimian et al., 2016; Steinbart et al., 2012; Steinbart et al., 2013). Leader E stated that it may be more appropriate for someone skilled in communication to mount an effective training and awareness campaign, and Leader G suggested the possibility that the person responsible for physical security could better give the institution a focus. The literature supports these ideas and recommends a holistic approach where computing security is represented in multiple disciplines within the organization (Soomro et al., 2016).

Recommendation four. A prioritized information security plan should be created that takes into account the current state of the institution as well as the prioritized recommendations in the adopted framework. Because there are limited resources available for computing security, priorities should be assigned to items in the computing security plan. The leaders unanimously agreed that resources were limited but most of the frameworks do not consider limited resources. In addition, the frameworks were not created with higher education in mind. Leader D has had some success with free and open source security tools and Leader H has outsourced security functions to augment their strategy. Both of these strategies acknowledge the need for focused and cost effective solutions.

Recommendation five. An aggressive and comprehensive user awareness and training program for computing security should be created. The literature is replete with works that state the need for user education and awareness programs (Hu et al., 2012; Parsons et al., 2013; Pfleeger & Caputo, 2012; Pfleeger et al., 2014; Rupere et al., 2012;

Solic et al., 2012). Only one of the IT leaders had a formalized user training program in place and all of the leaders acknowledged the risk associated with users and the need for more effective education.

Recommendation six. An environment of collaboration should be created for computing security on campus using both on-campus and off-campus resources. Leaders A, D, E, and F were all utilizing some sort of collaboration that either involves community resources or a multi-disciplinary committee on campus. It is interesting to note that the leaders in the study who were employing collaboration were also the most knowledgeable about computing security. The literature also recommends collaboration with outside resources for financial and knowledge enhancement purposes (Soomro et al., 2016).

Recommendation seven. A culture of computing security should be created on campus that involves every person in the organization. The need for a culture of security is supported in the literature as a means to leverage users of computing technology as an asset and defense against attackers (Paulsen, 2016; Posey et al., 2013). The interview data suggests that the leaders understood the weakness of their users but unfortunately, had not been able to broaden their vision to see them as a potential defensive asset.

Future research. The landscape is rich for future research into computing security at institutions of higher education. One of the most obvious avenues of research should include the development of a computing security framework or model specific to higher education. A variation of such a framework could focus on small and private institutions of higher education. Further research could also focus more specifically on the faculty side of the institution and what would be necessary for computing security

controls to be effectively implemented in their environment. Perhaps faculty and classroom resources should be isolated from the network similar to how most of the IT leaders in the study have approached the student network. Finally, more study should be focused on the computing security budgetary and human resources aspect of the operational barriers because of the prevalence of this theme during the interviews.

Conclusions

This study has focused on computing security in small and private institutions of higher education in the U.S. and has examined their unique operational impediments which prevent the implementation of sound computing security controls. Eight institutional computing security representatives were interviewed from the total population as part of a qualitative, multi-case study. The participants responded to questions that sought to understand operational impediments to computing security, current provisions of computing security that were lacking, and what resources would be necessary for effective security.

The interview data suggested a disorganized and piecemeal approach to computing security by the participants with varied successes and failures. The findings of the study, as shown in Table 15, indicate that there are significant operational barriers to computing security at these institutions as evidenced by the IT leader responses displayed in Tables four through eleven. A lack of comprehension and institutional support of computing security initiatives are evident in addition to an uncoordinated and piecemeal approach to computing security. Education for all levels of leadership along with the adoption of a formal framework is recommended as the critical first steps to address computing security.

Limitations of the study were considered that focused primarily on the sensitive nature of the research topic and the fear that the participants may not be candid in order to prevent a negative impression of themselves or the institution. However, the IRB requirement that the representatives be recruited as private citizens and their responses be treated as personal opinion seemed to promote more candid answers. Additionally, the interviews were not recorded and the participants were guaranteed confidentiality and anonymity which also seemed to promote openness of responses. Ethical considerations were taken into account by ensuring that the study was carried out in conjunction with IRB requirements. These requirements included full disclosure of the rights, risks, and responsibilities of the researcher and the participants as formalized in an informed consent document that was signed by the participants.

The implications of the study were considered in relation to the three research questions as shown in Table 16. The implications included a unique operational environment that was subject to significant barriers to computing security, a low priority for computing security from the perspective of all contingents on campus including IT leadership, an uncoordinated approach to computing security, a lack of comprehension by both IT leadership and senior leadership, and a lack of institutional support that was evident by insufficient resources and leadership support. The overall implications suggested that lack of comprehension and institutional support needed to be addressed as the underlying causes of insufficient computing security implementations.

The findings were placed in context with the study research problem and purpose and a linkage was established that corroborated the findings with the tension between user expectations and sound computing security practices at these institutions. The

significance of the study was highlighted as the realization of the importance of the pervasive threats to colleges and universities and the need for a coordinated and balanced approach to computing security. A contribution to the literature was discussed that argued for a gap related to a lack of attention to computing security within institutions of higher education. The practical utility of the study was presented as an instrumental work that brought to light the challenges and inadequacies faced by IT leaders in implementing computing security at these institutions. Recommendations and a concrete course of action were presented that consisted of the adoption of a computing security framework and continuing education of users, IT staff, IT leadership, and senior leadership as shown in Table 17. This study should aid in creating a foundational conversation that provides strategies and insights to personnel responsible for computing security and it should enable them to develop a vision that supports a holistic and organized approach.

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Appendix A: Interview Questions

1. What institutional traditions exist that interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere.
An example might be open library access.
2. What institutional philosophies exist that interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere.
An example might be academic freedom.
3. What operational aspects of the institution interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere.
An example might be distance learning initiative.
4. What specific technologies interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere.
An example might be email, wireless, cloud technologies, or web technologies
5. Are there any training issues that interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere.
An example might be refusal of departments to participate in training.
6. Are there any budgetary limitations that interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere.
An example might be insufficient funds to purchase a new firewall.
7. What political considerations exist that interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere.
An example might be lack of support for initiatives from direct supervisors or leaders of the college.

8. What human resource limitations exist that interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere. An example might be not having enough personnel to focus on computing security issues.
9. Are there any leadership deficiencies that interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere. An example might be a lack of understanding or priority given to computing security issues.
10. What student factors interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere. An example might be student complaints about computing security controls.
11. Are there any student entertainment factors that interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere. An example might be the insistence that no gaming features be blocked or bandwidth be throttled for these applications.
12. What other factors interfere with the implementation of information security controls best practices? Explain how and why they interfere.
13. What methods have been used by the institution to overcome any of these impediments?
14. What methods at computing security have been tried and failed?
15. What methods have only been marginally successful?
16. What additional resources would be necessary to implement adequate computing security at the institution?

17. What insights could be shared on how to effectively incorporate computing security measures in the institution?
18. What cautions could be shared about computing security at the institution?
19. What is your vision for computing security at your institution?
20. What other insights, perspectives, innovations or principles can you offer related to information security at your institution?

Appendix B: A Priori Codes

Traditions	TRA
Philosophies	PHI
Openness	OPN
Collaboration	COL
Political issues	POL
Operational technologies	OPR
Training issues	TRN
Human factor	HUM
Leadership issues	LED
Human resource issues	HR
Budgetary issues	BUD
Comprehension issues	COM
Entertainment issues - students	STU

Appendix C: Emergent Codes

Success	SUC
Failure	FL
Technologies - Useful	TEC
Innovation	INN
Insight	INS
Strategy	STR
Context	CON

Appendix D: Informed Consent Form

Introduction:

My name is Joseph Liesen. I am a doctoral student at Northcentral University. I am conducting a research study on information security issues in small and private institutions of higher education. I am completing this research as part of my doctoral degree. I invite you to participate.

Activities:

If you participate in this research, you will be asked to:

1. Participate in a telephone interview regarding information security issues at your institution.
2. Keep information regarding your interview confidential.

Eligibility:

You are eligible to participate in this research if you:

1. Are currently employed at a private institution of higher education in the U.S. with less than 5,000 on-campus students which confers at least a bachelor's degree.
2. You have direct involvement with information security at your institution, you oversee the information security function, or are the designated information security officer at your institution.

You are not eligible to participate in this research if you:

1. You do not meet the criteria above.
2. You do not have detailed knowledge of the information security function at your institution.

I hope to include representatives from eight institutions in this research.

Risks:

There are minimal risks in this study. A possible risk may consist of accidental interception of data from a third party (hacker) resulting in disclosure of your institutional data.

To decrease the impact of these risks, you can skip any question, and/or, stop participation at any time.

Benefits:

If you decide to participate, you will aid in bringing to light the innovations, insights and challenges related to information security at institutions of higher education. The potential benefits to others may consist of the formation of foundational discussion and strategy insights for the implementation of information security at institutions of higher education.

Confidentiality:

The information you provide will be kept confidential to the extent allowable by law. Some steps I will take to keep your identity confidential are Some steps I will take to keep your identity confidential are the inclusion of a fake name for your institution and ensuring that no information presented will allow the deduction of the name or location of you or your institution. Your name and your institution name will not reside in any of the research documents and will only be identifiable by a code. The code translation table will reside in the safe at all times until it is allowed to be destroyed per the guidelines of the Internal Review Board at Northcentral University. The people who will have access to your information are myself and my dissertation chair. The Institutional Review Board may also review my research and view your information.

I will secure your information by ensuring that your data is kept behind two locked doors and will reside in a safe. My research computer hard drive is encrypted so that your data cannot be accessed even if it is stolen.

I will keep your data for 7 years. Then, I will delete the electronic data and destroy the paper data.

Contact Information:

If you have questions for me, you can contact me at: J.Liesen4159@email.ncu.edu. My dissertation chair's name is Dr. Lee Ann Walker. She works at Northcentral University and is supervising me on the research. You can contact her at: leeanwalker@ncu.edu.

If you have questions about your rights in the research, or if a problem has occurred, or if you are injured during your participation, please contact the Institutional Review Board at: irb@ncu.edu or 1-888-327-2877 ext 8014.

Voluntary Participation:

Your participation is voluntary. If you decide not to participate, or if you stop participation after you start, there will be no penalty to you. You will not lose any benefit to which you are otherwise entitled.

Compensation:

To thank you for your willingness to participate, you will be given an Amazon gift card for \$25.

Additional Costs:

There are no anticipated financial costs to you.

Termination of Participation:

I may stop your participation, even if you did not ask me to, if I believe the information you are giving me is not truthful.

If you decide to stop participation, you may do so by sending me or my dissertation chair an email stating your desire to stop participation. If so, I will not use the information I gathered from you.

Signature:

A signature indicates your understanding of this consent form. You will be given a copy of the form for your information.

Participant Signature Printed Name Date

Researcher Signature Joseph J Liesen
Printed Name Date

If you will not obtain a signature, please delete the signature lines from the template.

If applicable, these sections must be added to your consent form, somewhere above the “signature” section: